

C O R T E X ²

D5.1 – CORTEX² requirements and deployment architecture version 1

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery/Continuous Deployment
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
HLA	High Level Architecture
MR	Mixed Reality

MVP	Most Valuable Player
NLP	Natural Language Processing
POC	Proof Of Concept
SDK	Software Development Kit
STT	Speech To Text
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VCAA	Video Compression and Alternative Appearance
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

Abstract

This deliverable details the project requirements based on three use cases carried by the pilots. It starts with a literary presentation of each use case's scenarios and then a more technical view to describe the main interactions of the end-users with the system. These foundations are used to extract different types of needs for the development of the CORTEX² framework. They cover functional, non-functional, social, ethical, legal and user device needs. This study also allowed to define a high-level architecture and to build an idea on the deployment environment. By going into these specifications, the development challenges of the framework become more apparent. It was then important to clarify the expectations of FSTP in order to balance the efforts between the developments in the project and the 3rd party contributions. At this stage of progress, the involvement of the partners is growing and consistent with the expertise and workload of each of them. Finally, the review of the development plan in view of this study confirms the provisional plan already established in the initial proposal.

Executive Summary

CORTEX² aims to deliver a next generation telecooperative framework based on extended Reality and artificial intelligence technologies. This document presents the use cases, related requirements and technical implications. The presentation follows the work of the consortium and presents the different phases.

The first step involves identifying all the requirements that go into the project, including those referring to user behavior and employed XR devices. Using an efficient use cases description to outline these needs can help to understanding the development process and to track the goals and deadlines. This phase is a very important part for the clear definition of the technical requirements of the project.

The next phase consists in extracting and listing all the requirements to ensure that are thorough and clear. An examination is carried out to group them into components that will be an integral part of the future framework.

Finally, the requirements are grouped into functionalities and modules to be developed in the general framework. We provide a high-level architecture that shows the necessary modules, interfaces and covered functionalities.

The CORTEX² project

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work primarily from home or change their work model to stay in business. Today, all the signs are that remote work is here to stay. But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

Existing services and applications aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration — from video conferencing systems to project management platforms — are not yet ready to efficiently and effectively support all types of activities. And extended reality (XR)-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

The mission of CORTEX² is to democratize access to the remote collaboration offered by next-generation XR experiences across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

To this aim, CORTEX² will provide the following:

- Full support for **augmented reality (AR) experiences** as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway.
- Resource-efficient **teleconferencing tools** through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents.
- Easy-to-use and powerful **XR experiences** with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for **multichannel semantic interpretation** and enhanced tools such as **virtual conversational agents** and **automatic meeting summarization**.
- Full **integration of internet of things (IoT) devices into XR experiences** to optimize interaction with running systems and processes.
- **Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption** by delivering the core system with **open APIs** and launching **open calls** to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment.

Overall, **we will invest a total of 4 million Euros in two open calls**, which will be aimed at

1. Recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX².
2. Engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths.
3. Assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases.

The CORTEX² consortium is formed by 10 organizations in 7 countries, which will work together for 36 months.

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1. Introduction

This document sums up the results of Task 5.1 “**U-X, requirements and pilots**” of Workpackage 5 “**Architecture and pilots**”. It describes the envisioned experiences that will be developed in the diverse pilots and synthesizes the functional and non-functional requirements of the CORTEX² digital workplace. It will be completed with the deliverable D5.5 “**CORTEX² requirements and deployment architecture - version 2**” which will document the detailed deployed architecture following the ongoing work in Task 5.2 “**XR architecture design and deployment**”. The present release focuses on the fundamentals and examines the needs of the project in its various aspects. The document encompasses all necessary requirements to build the CORTEX² framework: a remote cooperative work solution based on virtual reality, augmented reality and mixed reality, taking into account the heterogeneity of the target users' devices. These requirements cover both functional and non-functional architectural requirements; social, legal and ethical constraints including data security and privacy, in particular, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) initiated by the European Commission. The document also presents the high-level architecture resulting from the requirements analysis.

Please note that in this document the words “**Cortex**” and “**CORTEX²**” are interchangeable, for usage purposes “**Cortex**” is used in the specification of the architecture while “**CORTEX²**” is used in reference to projects itself.

1.1. Methodology

We followed a principled method, presented at the kick-off meeting, to produce the content of this deliverable. This method consists of several actions spread over the time dedicated to Task T5.1 “**U-X, requirements and pilots**”. First, we have clearly defined the use cases that our partners pilots want to exploit in line with their operating environments: Industrial Maintenance, Collaborative Training, and Business Meetings. These use cases have been subdivided into scenarios to facilitate prototyping and testing. Then each of these scenarios generated several requirements of the following types: functional, non-functional, social, legal, ethical, security and privacy. These needs were collected and analysed to produce a list of required features among several that are either mandatory, desired, or optional. The

mandatory features are essential features for the CORTEX² framework and must be developed. The desired features are preferred over the optional ones and can be developed to meet the specific needs of certain use cases but are not essential for the CORTEX² framework to function. The desired features can be developed by the partners of the consortium or delegated to 3rd party companies chosen during the FSTP calls. The optional requirements are intended to provide a feature roadmap for the improvement of the framework during the industrial exploitation. Based on these requirements and in accordance with the tasks of WP2 **“Multimodal collaborative space”**, we have grouped the mandatory functionalities into coherent software components in order to plan and optimize the implementation, simplify the inter-component interactions and the sharing of responsibilities between partners. The modular conception of the CORTEX² framework is represented in a high-level architecture in this document. To avoid any overlap or misunderstanding, CORTEX² framework provides a generic standard functionality than can be selectively used and updated by additional developers' code to build and deploy application-specific CORTEX² application. Therefore, the word platform stands in this document an operating CORTEX² solution such as those that will be developed by the pilots.

In parallel to the collection and organization of the technical requirements, we called on partners expertise in social, legal and ethical issues to list the critical aspects and possible risks from that perspective. While work on ethical, legal and social aspects of the framework is assigned to Work package 4 (mainly in Tasks 4.1 **“Ethical and legal inventory”** and Task 4.4 **“Analysis of psychosocial factors to optimize CORTEX²”**), we decided to take into account the requirements on ethical, legal and social aspects in the task T5.1 in order to avoid any conflict between a chosen technical solution and implementation and implicit or explicit ethical, legal or social rules to be observed in a later stage.

1.2. Main achievements

During this period, we have refined a comprehensive definition of the three use cases which will be deployed in the pilots. This definition led to a complete list of requirements, which are either use-case specific, or generic to the overall CORTEX² framework. A list of software components has been established which are mapped to a high-level architecture. Some of the

components will be developed in the frame of the project, and other leverage existing tools provided by the project partners such as Rainbow-Core¹ for data transportation, Linto² for voice transcription and uiTOP³ for IoT integration.

1.3. Future work

This task is finished but its results are used as input for the Task 5.2 “**XR Architecture design and deployment**” which will continue till **M34**. The essential objective of this task is to detail and implement the communication API between the components of the architecture while improving and validating each component in order to solve the associated technical challenges. We recommend continuous integration and testing to avoid bugs and errors. To this aim, the consortium will use a software implementation tool with CI support (GitLab, hosted by DFKI).

¹ <https://developers.openrainbow.com/>

² <https://linto.ai>

³ https://www.intracom-telecom.com/en/products/telco_software/IoT/IoT_orchestration_Platform.htm

2. Description of the use cases

Three use-cases are defined with different exploitation objectives and complementary functionalities covering three areas: industrial maintenance, remote training and teleconferencing for business meetings. They address a common challenge on collaboration for a real time remote cooperative work using extended reality technologies. XR will be a powerful asset to improve productivity in these areas, mainly by allowing to manipulate and interact with objects, such as a machines, furniture and tools, without moving them physically to the user's location. The usage of an immersive environment will facilitate in this cases cooperation and assistance to the achievement of the objectives of the user work without further efforts or intervention constraints. For example, a weather alert preventing a trip to the plant to make an important repair or a problem on a rocket thousands of miles away.

In anticipation of the testing and validation period, we decided to break down the use cases into subparts that we call scenarios, phases, or views (depending on the use case) where each one can be presented during the development phase and can be evaluated independently.

Table 1 lists the use cases and their scenarios, which will be the target of the three development camps planned for the software integration and demonstration.

To facilitate the reading of the use cases, each scenario is described by a technical view in the form of a table containing a use case diagram in reference to the UML standard. The objective is to describe only the interactions, from the system usage point of view, at particular moments in time during the scenario. This is to answer a simple question: how the user could accomplish a specific task once s/he is in front of the application?

To this end, this description is enhanced as much as possible by the functionalities that should help the user to execute a specific action. By convention, the table contains the preconditions that must be fulfilled when the user starts using the system and the postcondition that indicates the system states at the end of user task. It is described by a sequence of actions of the different actors involved in the scenario. For each actor action, there is one or more system responses depending on the number of processes triggered to accomplish the task. This is only indicative to help understand the actor-system relationship.

The graph completes this description by giving an overview of the users' interaction with the system. It is made around a main functionality of the scenario that we want to achieve. To avoid any confusion, we have used two relations: <<include>> which indicates the function that must be true for the current action to occur and the relation <<extend>> that shows a relation of inheritance, reuse of a function or a service to accomplish the given action. The coloured circles come from the idea that all the functions that belong to the same topic are in a specific package without the necessity to precisely identify them. This makes it easier to abstract, reuse and understand the scenario without having to go into details.

Table 1: Use cases

Use Case	Scenario	Description
Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance	IM1	A technician on the field receives assistance and can work hands free and head-up
Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance	IM2	AR environment for the remote expert
Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance	IM3	Cooperation with other participants (experts, customer or decision maker)
Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance	IM4	End of the maintenance intervention
VR Remote Training	RT1	A single-trainee training session. Participants: Trainer, Trainee
VR Remote Training	RT2	A multi-trainee training session. Participants: Trainer, several Trainees, Supervisor
VR Business Meetings	BM1	A coordinator customizes the virtual space and gives default permissions to invited participants.
VR Business Meetings	BM2	A meeting takes place with multiple participants using various devices.
VR Business Meetings	BM3	User and system action steps to close the meeting gracefully

2.1. Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance

This use case describes the use of a MR device by a technician during a maintenance operation of an industrial machine. Three types of actors are involved in the use case, using various devices from different locations. A technician is guided remotely by an expert and a third participant is called to control the maintenance operation via the collaboration space. The scenario implementation will highlight CORTEX² capability to handle 2D and 3D models

occurring in heterogenous devices at the same live session with high quality video rendering under limited network conditions and with the involvement of IoT services.

Figure 1: Remotely assisted AR industrial maintenance - comparison of CORTEX² approach to existing solutions

2.1.1. User stories

A machine is in failure at Rebecca’s site and the production is stopped. Ashley is the nearest technician available and gets to the site to solve the issue. Ashley knows well her job but doesn’t know this particular machine which has been installed recently. Ashley creates a CORTEX² collaboration space where she can interact with Gilbert for remote guidance. A decision has to be made at some point in the diagnosis which requires the involvement of Rebecca who is added into the collaborative space.

Personas

- Ashley: Technician for maintenance on machinery in industry and in particular in steel industry, evolving in noisy, risky and dirty environment
- Gilbert: senior machine expert, working from home as consultant for a company manufacturing industrial equipment
- Rebecca: Site director of the steel factory. On the move for a meeting, in a train.

Devices

- Mobile phone and see-through AR device for Ashley
- Laptop or desk PC with 3 high quality screens for Gilbert
- Mobile phone for Rebecca

i) Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance – Scenario 1

Ashley is a young maintenance technician who has recently joined a company, manufacturing and installing machines, in the steel industry. She was called by the support facility, through CORTEX² platform, for an emergency intervention in a nearby factory. Production has come to a complete halt due to a machine breakdown. All breakdown information and self-diagnosis of the machine were included to the call. Ashley can check them in her mobile phone or in her mixed reality device on which she can preview the intervention area. On this basis, she has now built a first idea of the problem.

Rebecca, the site manager, is travelling for an important meeting. She is on a train and has been notified about the breakdown. She joined the maintenance session via CORTEX² conference call to follow the progress of the repair in real time. On her way to the site, Ashley calls Gilbert, a maintenance expert, to get assistance. Gilbert works from home on his computer with 3 large screens. Optionally, Gilbert can be invited to the CORTEX² collaboration space based on his skills. When Ashley arrives at the company site; she is driven to the broken machine. With her mixed reality device, she connects to the CORTEX² collaboration space. She scans the machine with her MR device so that the recognition engine interconnected with her goggles can produce a virtual model of the industrial environment. As the 3D model of this machine is already uploaded in CORTEX² platform, it can now be rendered on Gilbert's device for in-depth view. Gilbert and Ashley can communicate hand free and take advantage of the noise suppressor embedded in the platform.

As this is about to be the beginning of the diagnosis, Ashley initiates the recording of the intervention by voice command.

ii) Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance – Scenario 2

Gilbert has loaded the troubleshooting information of the machine to his screens with the help of the virtual assistant. He knows the functioning and required maintenance actions of this machine but this new issue seems to be a bit more complicated. He wishes to have assistance in solving it.

By chance, this machine has been installed recently and equipped with several embedded IoT devices interconnected with the CORTEX² platform. Therefore, diagnosis data was automatically gathered and sent to Ashley together with the ticket information who in turn shared them with Gilbert. The 3D model of the machine is now augmented with data coming from IoT sensors. Ashley can see this information through her MR device and Gilbert can even execute, by voice, some commands through the highlighted actuators. Both Gilbert and Ashley can follow the feedback and the results instantaneously.

iii) Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance – Scenario 3

Now Ashley is on front of the machine and Gilbert can see everything she is looking at thanks to the camera embedded in her mixed reality device. But for more comfort, the scene is reconstructed at Gilbert side so that he can manipulate a 3D model to position it as required. Gilbert guides vocally Ashley to check some specific part of the machine. He follows the step-by-step description given in the machine manual. It is necessary to remove a cover from the machine to check a wiring and the procedure is a little complicated. To make it easier, Gilbert can see a local rendering of his hands while manipulating the model and have his movements captured so that he can record the exact actions to perform. The recording is pushed back to Ashley who can see the action superimposed on the real machine while hearing Gilbert's comments and reading Gilbert's annotations, Ashley can also consult selected diagrams pushed by Gilbert. At each stage, Ashley uses voice commands to ask CORTEX² to take an image of the scene in preparation for editing the job report and for summary purposes. Ashley can control the visualization of the various AR layers thanks to voice command.

iv) Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance – Scenario 4

The issue has been confirmed and requires the purchase of a specific item which is not covered by the maintenance contract. Gilbert and Ashley together with the team summarize the

situation to Rebecca. Thanks to CORTEX², in a low bandwidth environment, Rebecca, still can see Gilbert animated video appearances commenting the pictures taken during the analysis.

Ashley closes the intervention by vocal command which initiates the consolidation of the intervention report as well as the conversation summary that is distributed to all stakeholders of the call as well as recorded in the support system.

2.1.2. **Technical view**

Main Success Path: Emergency meeting because of a machine failure	Description: A technician on the field receives assistance and can work hands free and head-up
Pre-condition	Post-condition
<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Rebecca, Ashley and Gilbert have devices running- They are logged in CORTEX² platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Everybody in the team can look at the machine failure and start diagnosis- The recording of the operation is started
Actor actions	Platform response
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The support facility reported machine failure2. Ashley informs Rebecca about the machine breakdown3. Ashley invites Gilbert to the maintenance session4. Ashley scans the QR code of the machine and shares its 3D model with Rebecca and Gilbert5. Ashley records the session to get the minutes automatically	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.1 Ashley is informed2.1 Notification forwarded to Rebecca3.1 Invitation is sent4.1 Screen sharing started5.1 Recording started

Main Success Path: Remote machine diagnosis	Description: AR environment for the remote expert
Pre-condition	Post-condition
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ashley and Gilbert have devices running - They are logged in CORTEX² platform - A machine failure is detected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The machine diagnosis is over
Actor actions	Platform response
1. Ashley shares IoT failure data and machine 3D model with Gilbert	1.1 Information are available to Gilbert 2.1 AR scene is updated 3.1 Action accomplished successfully

2. Gilbert loads IoT information and 3D model about the machine and can see its augmented 3D model
3. Gilbert can use virtual actuators to diagnose the machine

<p>Main Success Path: have the expert's hand actions superimposed on the real machine</p>	<p>Description: Cooperation with other participants (experts, customer or decision maker)</p>
<p>Pre-condition</p>	<p>Post-condition</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ashley and Gilbert have devices running - They are logged in CORTEX² platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the repair procedure

Actor actions	Platform response
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gilbert and Ashley activate the virtual assistant to interact with CORTEX² application using speech commands 2. Gilbert consults the machine manual 3. Gilbert selects the appropriate diagram 4. Gilbert starts recording virtual repairing sequence, a mixture of his hands and 3D machine model. 5. Gilbert shares the recording with Ashley 6. Ashley applies the markup on the real machine to fix the failure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1 Virtual assistant activated 2.1 Machine manual loaded and summarized into the screen, 2.2 Document browsing available 3.1 Diagram selected 4.1 Recording starts 4.2 Recording file saved 5.1 File shared with Ashley 6.1 File loaded by Ashley 6.2 superposition done 6.3 3D model can be manipulated

Main Success Path: Ashley closes the maintenance meeting	Description: End of the maintenance intervention
Pre-condition	Post-condition
<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Rebecca, Ashley and Gilbert have devices running- They are logged in CORTEX² platform- The repair procedure was identified	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Maintenance intervention is over
Actor actions	Platform response
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Ashley and Gilbert summarize the maintenance session with any evidence2. Ashley requests the report using voice command and made it available to participants3. Rebecca can consult the maintenance report4. Ashley closes the meeting	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.1 audio call is registered1.2 screenshot included to the meeting folder2.1 the report is available3.1 the report is loaded in Rebecca screen4.1 the meeting is closed

2.2. VR Remote Training

The training use case is based on an existing client-solution developed by Actimage which is used for introductory VR trainings on excavators. The current solution, however, only allows a single-user offline training. If the trainee encounters problems during the training or has any questions, it might not be possible for them to get support easily. The developments planned for within the CORTEX² framework should help to mitigate this problem. The described training use cases sketch how the training scenario could be realised within CORTEX². The goal is to open the VR training environment to other participants, first and foremost a trainer that remotely participates in training classes and can give advice whenever needed. Scenario 1 describes how a virtual training like this could be performed. In addition, connecting trainees virtually also

offers the possibility to open the current single-user lessons to several participants at the same time. Scenario 2 describes a VR training with several trainees and one trainer in a virtual classroom. In this later, both group classes and single-user training sessions are possible.

The following figure illustrates the two scenarios with regards to already existing VR training solution.

Figure 2: VR remote training - comparison of CORTEX² approaches to existing solutions

2.2.1. User Stories

Personas

The following personas were identified as users of the application planned for the training scenario. In addition to the listed personas, other training participants with a similar background as Jane are assumed for Use Case 2.

- Jane: trainee, working for a construction company, wants to learn how to handle their new excavator

- Thomas: trainer, working for the excavator's constructor as a professional trainer on their machines
- Maria: Thomas's supervisor, head of the training department of the excavator's constructor, responsible for training quality and customer satisfaction with the training programme

Devices

In order to ensure an effective and positive learning and teaching experience, the personas in the training use cases should be equipped with the following devices:

- PC with camera (trainer, supervisor)
- VR device (trainees)

I. VR Remote Training - Scenario 1

Jane just arrived at work. Today, she starts the training program for her new excavator license. She already knows how to use other, similar machines, but the model she will learn about today is brand-new and the pride and joy of her team. Her instructor for today will be Thomas, a professional trainer at the training centre of the excavator company.

Since Jane and Thomas are located in two different countries and the excavator is currently in use on the construction site, they will perform a virtual remote training with VR. This avoids long travels for Jane and Thomas and does not require taking the excavator out of service for the time of the training. Since Jane's company does not possess any VR headset, Thomas sent a suitable headset that is ready for use to Jane's office last week.

For Jane, it is her first remote training with a VR headset and she is a bit nervous. However, she is used to have normal video-conference meetings with Rainbow every week. That's why she was relieved to receive a usual invitation link for her training from Thomas. They both start the meeting as a video conference and Thomas explains Jane, how to wear the VR headset and adjust it for a perfect fit. Once Jane is ready, Thomas starts the headset and the introduction lesson of the training programme using a written command in a control-chatbot channel of the videoconference tool.

Jane sees the training environment in her VR glasses now. She can also hear Thomas's voice through the VR headset speakers and depending on the settings that Thomas configured in his training client application, can see either a video stream of Thomas or a 2D avatar of Thomas that shows his mimics. Her laptop's speakers and microphone were muted automatically when the training lesson in the headset started to avoid acoustic feedback.

Thomas chooses the difficulty of the lesson according to Jane's level and understanding using the Rainbow UI. He can also change settings of the lesson like the level of explanations and instructions in the lesson. Thomas himself hears Jane's voice and sees what Jane can see through her VR glasses. In addition, he can also navigate himself through the 3D world of the training lesson on his PC screen.

Thomas accompanies Jane through her training lesson, he explains her the different training tasks and helps her out when she is stuck. He can orally give her hints and background knowledge when needed. Jane interacts with the environment of the 3D world and learns how to handle the new excavator in a hands-on way. Everything Jane and Thomas say is analysed by an automatic voice recognition. Once they finished the tasks of the training lesson, both Jane and Thomas get a summary what they did and spoke. Like this, Jane can revise what she learned and Thomas knows what they have already done for preparing the next session.

Jane and Thomas do several sessions divided into training lessons. Since Jane learns really quickly, Thomas decides to start a more advanced lesson than originally planned. This lesson is not yet stored locally on the VR headset. He sends the content of the lesson to Jane's VR headset via Rainbow and then starts it locally on the headset.

Jane is happy about today's training. She could learn about all of the important aspects of her new excavator in a very practical way. In addition, she has her training notes that help her to remember the most important points of each training lesson. Also, Thomas likes the new training method using CORTEX² because he can do more trainings without having to travel all the time. The application offers an easy and intuitive way of handling all of his training participants and allows him to track the training process for all of his trainees easily.

II. VR Remote Training - Scenario 2

Sometimes, Thomas also gives training lessons with several participants in one training session. This often happens for more advanced groups that are already familiar with the training application. The topic of the training lesson is often more theory-heavy and contains both a theoretical and a practical part. Typical examples are an annual security lesson or advanced topics like an energy-efficient use of the excavators.

All of the participants are connected to the session with their VR headsets and can see and hear each other's avatar and Thomas's face or his avatar in the 3D world. They first meet in a virtual classroom to work on the theoretical part of the lesson. Thomas usually gives a presentation about today's topic. To do so, he shares the screen of his computer where he opened the presentation. His screen is then shown to the participants on a virtual screen in their 3D world.

After the presentation, every participant practices the practical part of the lesson on their own. To do so every participant is moved to a separate virtual training space where they don't hear and see the other participants anymore. They can do their practical training lesson by interacting with the 3D representation of their excavator and following the training scenario's steps.

If they need help or advice, they can raise their hand and Thomas gets notified. He can then switch to the respective participant's session and help them out. This allows Thomas to watch several individual trainings in parallel. Thomas can change the sound and room options for the participants, i.e., he can change audio channels of all participants to a common channel where they can discuss problems together. Also, he can decide when the individual training is over and move all participants back to the classroom.

In order to assure the quality of the training Thomas conducts, his supervisor Maria sometimes participates in a training session. She can login to the training and observe what is said and done, but not participate in the discussion. The main objective of this is to provide feedback to Thomas after his training session.

2.2.2. **Technical view**

In the described use case scenarios, in total three types of actors can be identified: trainers, trainees and supervisors. In scenario two, there might be several trainees participating in the

same training session. Each of the identified actors has several different actions that they can take in order to start a training or during the training session. The following tables describe conditions, actions and actors for each of the two use cases and present a use case diagram specifying possible actions for each actor.

Main Success Path: Single-trainee training session	Description: Training session with one trainee and one trainer. The trainee uses a VR device, the trainer their PC/Laptop
Pre-condition	Post-condition
- Thomas and Jane are authenticated by CORTEX ² using PC and VR devices respectively	- Training session ends and training notes are sent to Jane
Actor actions	Platform response
1. Thomas sends an invitation link to Jane 2. Thomas sets preferences and difficulties of the lesson 3. Thoms share the lesson with Jane 4. Jane starts session recording to get lesson notes at the end of training. 5. Jane reviews and download the lesson notes	1.1 link forwarded to Jane 2.1 Lesson setup 3.1 Lesson shared with Jane

<p>Main Success Path:</p> <p>Training lessons with several participants</p>	<p>Description: Training session with one trainer and several trainees. Additionally, a supervisor may follow the trainer’s performance.</p>
<p>Pre-condition</p>	<p>Post-condition</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thomas has already prepared and stored training scenes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The training session ends
<p>Actor actions</p>	<p>Platform response</p>

1. Thomas and participants join the virtual room
2. Thomas loads and share his presentation
3. Thomas can setup training session for each participant
4. Each participant can have a standalone training lesson
5. A participant can ask question by raising hand.

- 1.1 authentication process succeeds
- 2.1 screen sharing started
- 3.1 New parameters are taken into account
- 4.1 Private session activated
- 5.1 Notification message sent to Thomas

2.3. VR Business Meeting

The objective of this use case is to build a videoconferencing solution that bring in technological advances in virtual reality for the context of teleworking. Teleworking is seen as a gain in quality of life because it avoids the often long and tiring journeys. It allows the company to be more agile and efficient because the teams are no longer formed on the basis of geographical proximity but on the basis of adequacy to the objective.

We expect from this use case to increase productivity by leveraging new virtual reality, artificial intelligence and voice recognition technologies and wish to accentuate the cohesion between the team members through virtual presence, giving them a sense of presence close to the truth. Moreover, this use case will help to understand the usage impact of new XR and AI-guided technologies on the performance of teamwork. LINAGORA is already working on the development of a collaborative, open-source platform dedicated to teamwork called Twake⁴, and a speech recognition technology called Linto⁵ with a focus on business meetings domain, but are limited in comparison to the freedoms that a user can have in a virtual world such as working around a 3D model object. Besides, this use case will help to provide a credible open-source alternatives that are more inclusive, sustainable, ecologically favourable, and promotes the integration of disabled workers.

2.3.1. **User Stories**

The story does not describe internal aspects and shows only the process from the point of view of the actors in three use cases. The story explores alternative ways of interaction during meetings between multiple remote workers using heterogeneous devices.

Personas

- Maria: meeting organizer, working for a new project
- Jane, Liz, Thomas and John: participating to the meeting

Devices

- PC with camera (Maria, organizer)

⁴ <https://twake.app>

⁵ <https://linto.ai/>

- VR device (Jane, Liz and Thomas)
- Smart phone (John)

i) Virtual Business Meeting Scenario 1

Jane is at her office starting her workday. Today she has a business meeting with her boss Maria and her colleagues John, Liz, and Thomas. Maria and John are out of town in a business trip, and Liz and Thomas are at home teleworking. For the last three months they have been using the CORTEX² platform for their business meetings. Maria sent them a link to connect to the meeting yesterday. For this meeting, Maria has activated COVA, the CORTEX² Virtual Assistant.

ii) Virtual Business Meeting Scenario 2

Jane connects from her desktop and put on the VR headset (oculus quest 2). Now everybody at the office has its own, so they can take it home when teleworking. Jane also wears a sensor in her hands. Everybody is connecting now. Upon connection she is asked by COVA the authorization to listen and access to the meeting. Liz wears also her VR headset and hand sensors from home. Apart from the meeting she must pay attention to her cell phone because she is expecting an important call from one of her customers. Thomas is also wearing his VR headset and using his desktop at home, but not the hand sensors. Maria is at a hotel room using her laptop and John is using his smartphone from his rental car. They do not wear the CORTEX² devices.

Figure 3: Virtual business meeting - comparison of CORTEX² approach to existing solutions

Everybody is at the VR conference now. The different avatars sit around the table. Jane feels now in a 3D space. She is in a virtual room. It is a conference room with a big screen for presentations. The feeling is as a first-person perspective (like in the videogames). Jane can see the avatars of her colleagues and COVA's avatar sitting around the table. There are other empty chairs, today is not a crowded meeting. The faces of the avatars are very similar to her colleagues' faces. The avatars of Jane and Liz can also move their hands. Jane can see her VR hands and they move at the same time and in the same way than hers, which is cool. Maria shares her screen to show the slides that will guide the meeting. All can see the presentation in the VR big screen. The meeting goes well. All the conversation is in English. On some occasions, Thomas prefers writing down in the chat to avoid the noise around him and a conversational assistant pops out and tell us what Thomas is writing. At a certain moment, there is a sign on the big screen for Liz, her smart phone is ringing. She leaves the meeting for some minutes and then she comes back. Jane also shares her screen to show some administrative documents. Liz asks COVA to find an information about a new customer in the documents in the group shared folder and to share it. Maria accesses the summary of the documents related to the conversation prepared by COVA. John asks if this customer also has activities in the US. COVA hears this question and search the internet. As there is a short silence, it speaks out the answer it found.

iii) Virtual Business Meeting Scenario 3

The meeting lasts 50 minutes. Jane is happy because she does not have to write the minutes of the meeting. COVA does that for her. Maria can access the conversation manager service where she can find the summary of the meeting. She can update and share it with other documents, Maria wants everybody to have. Jane takes out the VR glasses. It takes a little time to get used to the real world again. She has been totally immersed in the meeting. She likes this system because it is much easier to concentrate in the meeting and not get distracted by other things happening at the office or the usual distractors (colleagues passing by, WhatsApp, email, etc.). So far, CORTEX² is working well for her and her colleagues.

2.3.2. Technical view

In what follows, a visible interaction between an actor and the CORTEX² solution is presented to show how an actor uses this system to achieve a goal. The different paths that can be taken by an actor to achieve a specific goal are represented as a narrative (use case table description) or as a visual model (use case diagram figure).

Main Success Path: Creation of the meeting room	Description: A coordinator customizes the virtual space and gives default permissions to invited participants.
Pre-condition	Post-condition
<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Maria is already authenticated by CORTEX² app as a meeting organizer- Maria is using laptop, Jane, Liz and Thomas are using VR headsets, John smart-phone.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Room meeting is created and can be rendered in VR and laptop devices- All participants received the meeting link and can connect to CORTEX² platform
Actor actions	Platform response
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Maria creates the meeting room by selecting the default VR scene or loading other one from CORTEX² database2. Maria defines default roles of the participants3. Maria shares the link of the meeting with other participants (Jane, John, Liz, and Thomas)	1.1 VR scene is configured to be used with the defined meeting.

<p>Main Success Path: Participating to the meeting</p>	<p>Description: A meeting takes place with multiple participants using various devices.</p>
<p>Pre-condition</p>	<p>Post-condition</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jane, Liz, and Thomas have logged in and their avatars sit around the table - Audio, text and video conferencing support - Maria and John appear in video stream - Scene room contains a big screen for slides sharing - Scene room contains a non-VR users screen to render video stream avatar, user icon or user image 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meeting audio is recorded - All the participants are logged out

<p>- The virtual assistant appears as an avatar sitting around the Table</p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Maria loads the slides2. Maria activates the virtual assistant3. The virtual assistant asks for authorization to participate to the meeting.4. Maria starts screen sharing5. Maria starts the presentation using audio communication6. Jane raises her avatar hand7. Thomas writes a comment8. Liz receives a call9. Liz leaves temporary the meeting10. Liz comebacks to the meeting11. Jane has now the sharing rights and can present her document and starts presenting it.12. Jane asks the virtual assistant to find extra information13. The meeting ends	<ol style="list-style-type: none">2.1 the slides are displayed for all participants3.1 All participants are listening to Maria4.1 VR users see the hand-up of Jane, other users receive a notification5.1 Thomas comment is turned into a voice using speech technology.5.2 All participants can hear Thomas comment.6.1 The ring is detected6.2 A notification appears in Liz scene7.1 Liz status is changed to absent for non-VR users and a pinned notification is shown on her avatar.8.1 Liz status is updated9. Presentation screen is updated to Jane shared documents

<p>Main Success Path: Closing the meeting</p>	<p>Description: User and system action steps to close the meeting gracefully</p>
<p>Pre-condition</p>	<p>Post-condition</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The meeting has taken place as planned by Maria The meeting is closed and the audio is recorded 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Every participant has received the meeting summary
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Maria requests the meeting summary from the virtual assistant Maria updates the summary if necessary 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1 The speech recognition service receives the meeting audio and starts processing for summarization and gives it

2.4. Open call and exploratory use cases or features

In the frame of the foreseen Financial Support to Third Parties, the CORTEX² framework will be used to implement additional Use-Cases that are not known at this stage. The proposals for

additional Use-Cases can be made by small consortia of several partners, combining a Use-Case owner and technical partners who will develop new features. During the use case description and requirements collection phase, the consortium made an effort to collect generic requirements that would cover the needs of additional use cases. The derived functionalities will be implemented in a way to accommodate for possible new necessary features coming from the additional use-cases. The additional features will be co-developed by the third parties with the support and expertise of the partners in the consortium.

Examples for possible additional use cases are:

- Virtual reality for crisis management in case of disaster.
- Collaborative working on N-dimensional data
- Virtual presence solution for a company remote worker.

3. Requirements

The requirements are collected in a document that describes what the software will do and how it should work. These are features and functionalities of the target system drawn from scenarios of section **Error! Reference source not found.** They express the users' expectations of the final product and they give a complete picture of the entire project. It also provides a roadmap that each team involved in the development will follow and keeps all teams in sync with the goals and operation of the software prototypes to be implemented by the pilots.

This is also important for all partners of the project to fully encompass the subject and determine who needs to be involved because inadequate definition of the requirements and responsibilities can lead to major problems, both in financial terms and extra development time.

3.1. Collection

The collection procedure consists in sharing a document among partners for data gathering and use cases analysis. This process mainly involves the pilots to ensure that their objectives are taken into account. Each use case can be subdivided into a set of simple and independent phases to facilitate the testing and validation of the associated features. CORTEX² pilots are described by one table that lists the use cases and the corresponding scenarios illustrated in

Table 1.

3.2. Functional requirements

Each requirement is described by a set of properties as indicated in the Figure 2. This information allows to easily identify the requirement, its owner, its priority, any conflicts with other requirements and possibly suggestions or remarks about it.

Functional_Requirement
+ ID: string
+ Description: string
+ Rational: string
+ Priority: Level [0..3]
+ Elicited_By: <<Partner>
+ Comment_Question_Issue: string
+ Conflecting_requirement: string

Figure 4: Structure of a requirement

Requirements prioritization is an important attribute to enable delivery optimization and to ensure that requirements quantity does not exceed the team's ability to execute the work. Priority includes three categories: mandatory, desired and optional, introduced in Section 1.1. In this project, the main attention is given to mandatory requirements to maintain the objectives that highest value features are delivered first, minimizing product risk associated with delivery. Desired and optional features can be developed in part within the FSTP call or developed later by each partner depending on its future exploitation plan.

A complete list of the functional requirements is provided in Annex A. In the following, we categorize the requirements in specific sets and provide a description of the main needs:

3.2.1. User role and access Management

These requirements are means for the organizer of the remote cooperation session to define how to interact via videoconferencing and the role that each one will carry out during the meeting. In CORTEX² applications, access is generally granted by invitation and there is always an initiator who administers the session. There could also be observer-members, i.e., they do not intervene in the collaborative work. Furthermore, there is no role for system-resources monitoring nor administration rules for security and confidentiality checking. Only basic needs in terms of privacy and security are considered. This last point is detailed in Section 3.5.4. The

assignment of roles varies depending on the application. We have for example, three pilots where we find trainees, trainer, technician, expert, etc. All the smartness of CORTEX² application is in the way to achieve the functionalities according to the role of the actor. The work started in task T2.1 covers these aspects and ensures that the users are able to perform their role in the application and have all the functionalities at their disposal.

3.2.2. **Standard videoconference requirements**

These requirements cover the common functionalities of a video conferencing solution which are audio, video and document sharing. However, through these needs, CORTEX² extends the notion of sharing to make it more interactive i.e., members are not only spectators but can interact and manipulate remote objects using XR and IoT technologies, as in the case of industrial maintenance where a 3D modelling of a machine through AR device will help to identify its functionalities and accomplish maintenance operation remotely. The novelty and the challenge at the same time, is also in the capacity to be able to accomplish these functions in a heterogeneous environment associating XR and legacy devices.

Concerning live chat, the analysis has identified the importance of voice synthesis and recognition. It appears that in some use cases, the operator's hands are busy and the only option for him is to dictate the message vocally. In another case, it is assumed that there is a problem with the micro-phone of one attendee so the message is written and then synthesized for the other members.

3.2.3. **XR requirements**

XR requirements are at the heart of this project. In addition to enabling an immersive collaboration environment, it is about being able to scan real-world objects in 3D and being able to determine some of their features while augmenting them with useful information for the user. These needs cover avatar generation which also reduce the bandwidth when attendees activate their camera streaming. Besides, this feature is seen as a way to enhance privacy for people who do not want to show their face and what is around them.

3.2.4. **Virtual assistant requirements**

In CORTEX², the requirements related to this technology are first of all related to autonomic meeting/document summarization and memo generation. The use of a virtual assistant

emphasizes also this need to satisfy user assistance demands and interaction with attendees using speech. Voice recognition and synthesis are essential as mentioned in the previous sections. For example, pilot 3 planned to use virtual assistance when searching documents. Other pilots intended to use the assistant for executing some commands, etc.

3.2.5. Requirements for IoT interface

The interaction with the real world is done through the materialization of real objects in the virtual world. This requires the XR features, already mentioned, to allow sharing and manipulation of the object in the virtual world by several users. The IoT also comes into play to render the user sensors and actuators in the virtual space for a particular purpose. The pilots leave open the use of IoT for this second situation, for a possible integration in the case of the Financial Support for Third Parties call (FSTP), for example, to be informed at any time about the status of the smoke sensor or to activate the door opener if someone rings the doorbell. The door camera is streamed to the user's virtual space and the door can be opened just by a button.

3.2.6. Interaction requirements

These requirements put forward advanced interaction functionalities based on the great contribution of VR, displaying objects with a complete 3D view but not only. IoT needs complete them by making the objects alive in the virtual world, i.e., having their states and acting on their interfaces. Interaction requirements go beyond this to allow avatars of participants showing user actions like hand raising to express the desire to talk in a meeting. Concerning the user intention, the scenarios did not specify mandatory requirements because it was necessary to make a balance on the objectives. Being very ambitious can imperil the development. However, the planned calls for Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) will allow for planning extensions, in particular, the detection of intention to anticipate certain actions. Moreover, the presence of a virtual assistant advocates not only a gestural interaction of the user but also verbal actions. This latter is supported in the requirements expressed in section 3.2.4 above.

3.2.7. Devices compatibility

The challenge for a CORTEX² application is to be able to run on different devices where compatibility is not always guaranteed. For this purpose, the requirements have been

addressed through a comparative analysis, presented in Section 3.4. Only the devices with the most desired specifications are retained. The question of the ability to interface the devices with the IoT objects also remains an essential element if you want to connect the object directly to the application without going through IoT servers. In some cases, such as traveling by train, it is no longer possible to connect to the train broadcasting service through IoT server to get informed about the name of the next stations. On the other hand, it would be possible to connect to this service directly from the application by clicking on the broadcasting link provided by the transportation service. Task 2.3 **“AV/AR Devices connectivity, interfaces and standardization”** investigates this kind of situations and other issues. In addition, the common factor in these requirements is the ability to use the browser as a vehicle for the CORTEX² applications, especially because it is available and accessible from the majority of XR devices. This somewhat facilitates interoperability between CORTEX² XR applications and the legacy Rainbow video-conferencing solution, but this should not prevent the need to allow users using different tools and devices to communicate and collaborate with each other.

3.3. Non-Functional requirements

Non-functional requirements are constraints on the services or functions offered by the system such as time constraints, constraints on the development process, standards, etc. They are usually defined on the system as a whole. They have the same structure as functional requirement and are presented in Annex B. These requirements deal with the behaviour of the application with respect to the final result to the user. It was difficult to enumerate these requirements since it is a collaborative development that involves very different partners' experience and tools. The partners often master and bring proprietary solutions that make it difficult to imagine the specification of the requirements without prior testing. For example, it would be unreasonable to force a particular language or a unique development framework. Compromises in this case are more favoured to meet the objectives of all partners. Thus, each partner has brought some requirements that are related to their involvement. We categorize them as follows:

- **Non-functional requirements on the server-side** draw attention to the deployment environment and its performance in supporting a large number of users and IoT objects.

From experience, despite the speculation on these numbers, the real use of the solution shows very different values. These needs will evolve very well when we will be confronted with the real development.

- **Non-functional requirements on the application side** are elements related to the multi-modal use of the application, i.e., by gestures, actions on a button, speech, etc. Especially in a virtual space and with a very diversified mode, the application must be able to update quickly the states associated to the interactions. For example, if the audio is activated by a voice command, the corresponding buttons must change its status, otherwise it can confuse the user and his private discussions will be listened.
- **Non-functional requirement for multi-view application usage.** What is difficult with a collaborative application is the fact of having a multitude of views in adequacy with the intended use and the role of the co-worker. The requirements in this context raise the problem of inter-view interaction to get cooperative work done with consistency.

3.4. [VR/AR devices](#)

One of the challenges of this project is the strong dependency between software and hardware. Since the requirements postulate the use of different devices by the users and there is a wide range of XR devices with different or complementary capabilities, it was therefore essential to establish compatibility between the developments and the users' execution environment in order to support a wide possible range of devices. Some needs may indeed have a direct impact on the choice of AR or VR device if the required rendering is not supported or shows a lack of performance. Thus, an alignment should be done in order to avoid unexpected outcomes during the tests. Accordingly, we have established in Table 2 a list of basic criteria for CORTEX² framework and in Table 3 the selected devices that could be part of pilots' demonstrations.

Table 2: Device Requirements

Requirement	Description
Stand-alone device	Refer to a device that can operate on its own, without requiring add-on or plug-in

Unity Integration	Whatever the decision on framework, best if compliant. Check if Unity WebRTC compliant
Video Pass-through	Maintenance pilot requires mixed reality (VR headset with external cameras for blending real and virtual)
Price	2000€ seems a maximum - Under 1000€ more realistic for future customer projects
Max Field of View	Maximum area sensor can capture at a given lens focal length of lens.
Max Resolution (per eye)	4K would be a plus, HD can cover the current use cases.
Screen Type	LCD is standard and ok
Pixel Density	Pixels per inch (ppi) and pixels per centimetre (ppcm or pixels/cm) are measurements of the pixel density of an electronic image device
Sensors	A computer processor that detects events or changes in its environment
Max Refresh Rate	The maximum number of frames a monitor can display per second
Tracking	Tracking of the device in 6 DOF (degrees of Freedom).
Weight	None
Extra Requirements	None

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Table 3: Headset comparison

	Stand-alone device	Unity integration	Video Passthrough	Price	Max Field of View	Max resolution (per eye)	Screen Type	Sensors	Max refresh rate	Tracking	Weight	Other specification
Meta Quest 2	Yes	Yes	Yes	400\$	97°	1832x1920	LCD	Accelerometer, gyroscope, Internal Cameras	120Hz	6DOF Inside Out via 4 integrated cameras	503g	Hand tracking
HTC Vive Focus3	Yes	Yes	Yes	1300\$	120°	2448x2448	LCD	Accelerometer, gyroscope, Internal Cameras	90Hz	6 DoF Inside-out via 4 integrated cameras	785g	Hand tracking
Meta Quest Pro	Yes	Yes	Yes	1500\$	106°	1800x1920	LCD	3 Wider FoV World Cameras, Depth Camera, RGB Camera, Ambient Light Sensor, 4x Eye Tracking Cameras	90Hz	6 DoF Inside-out via 5 integrated cameras	722g	Eye, hand and Face tracking
Varjo XR-3	No	Yes	Yes	7840\$	115°	2880x2720	LCD	Built-in LiDAR	90Hz	6 DoF Marker-based or inside-out tracking	980g	Hand and eye tracking
Lynx R1	Yes	Yes	Yes	1300\$ (pro)	90°	1600x1600	LCD	Accelerometer, gyroscope, Internal Cameras (B&W / IR)	90Hz	6 DoF Inside-out via 2 integrated cameras	500g	Hand tracking (EU-FR)
Meta Quest 3	Yes	Yes	Yes	500\$	105°	1920x1800	OLED	optical internal and external cameras, LiDAR depth sensor	120Hz	inside-out via cameras	TBA	face, hand, body and eye tracking
Microsoft HoloLens	Yes	Yes	Yes	3000\$	30°	1268x720	LCoS	Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer	60Hz	6 DoF Inside-out via 4 integrated cameras	579g	Hand tracking
Microsoft HoloLens 2	Yes	Yes	Yes	3500\$	52°	1440x936	LBS	Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer,	60Hz	6 DoF Inside-out via 4 visible light cameras and 2 Infrared cameras	556g	Hand and eye tracking

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								Internal Cameras (IR)				
Pico 4 XR	Yes	Yes	Yes	490\$	105°	2160x2160	LCD	Nine-axis sensor, P-sensor, Hall sensor, motor controller	90Hz	6 DoF Inside-out via 5 integrated cameras	586g	2 broadband haptic motion controllers
Varjo Aero	No	Yes	No	2000\$	115°	2880x2720	LED	The external tracking sensors	90Hz	6 DoF Marker-based	717g	Eye tracking
Magic Leap 1	Yes	Yes	Yes	2295\$	50°	1280x960	Photonic lightfield chip	Accelerometer and Gyroscope Sensors	120Hz	6 DoF Inside-out	316g	Eye and hand tracking
Magic Leap 2	Yes	Yes	Yes	3299\$	70°	1440x1760	Liquid crystal on silicon (LCoS)	IMU, Accelerometer and Gyroscope Sensors	120Hz	6 DoF Inside-out	260g	Eye and hand tracking
TCL Ray Neo X2	Yes	Not Available	Yes	unreleased	25°	NA	LED	gyroscope, accelerometer, compass, and pressure sensor	NA	6 DoF Inside-out	NA	None
Nreal Air	No	Yes	Yes	400\$	46°	1920x1080	OLED	Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer Proximity sensor	90Hz	3 DoF Non-positional	76g	None
EPSON BT-40s	Yes	Yes	Yes	1094\$	34°	1920x1080	OLED	Compass, gyroscope, accelerometer, light sensor	60Hz	3 DoF Non-positional	96g	None
Vuzix Clade 2	Yes	Yes		1380\$	20°	480x480	Wave Guide Projection			3 DoF Non-positional	90g	None

							Technology.					
HTC Vive XR Elite	Yes	Yes	Yes	1099\$	110°	1920x1920	LCD	4x Tracking cameras, 16 MP RGB camera, Depth sensor, G-sensor, Gyroscope, Proximity sensor	90Hz	6 DoF Inside-out via 4 integrated cameras. Also includes depth sensor	625g	Hand tracking

The main elements to be considered for the choice of a device are the price, the integrated features in terms of functionalities and sensors, and the quality of the rendering/video display in case of passthrough devices. After consideration of these elements, the consortium decided to opt for following devices for the implementation of the use cases:

- AR device: Lynx R1
- VR device: Meta Quest Pro

3.5. Extended CORTEX² requirements

Although extended reality technology is rapidly achieving some level of maturity and widespread adoption, there are still a lot of unknown risks for the users of XR, bystanders and society at large.[1] This section of the deliverable provides a preliminary inventory of the ethical and legal issues that are relevant to CORTEX² in order to devise the suitable architecture and requirements for the design and development of the CORTEX² framework. In addition, some components of the CORTEX² framework will be powered or enhanced by Artificial intelligence and this raises additional legal and ethical issues. The point here is to identify the legal and ethical risks and highlight various legal and ethical requirements that should be accounted for in the design and development of CORTEX². The issues identified in this section will be further addressed in D4.1 which would contain a more concrete evaluation of these legal and ethical considerations.

This section is made up of two clusters, highlighting the potential legal and ethical concerns raised by this immersive technology and the artificial intelligence components in CORTEX². The first cluster will focus on the ethical issues, while the second cluster will dive into the legal issues, with particular emphasis on the existing privacy and data protection framework in Europe and the EU. The legal concerns are based on the fundamental right to privacy and data protection as enshrined in the Council of Europe, the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR), the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU) and the General data protection regulation (GDPR). Although the high-level analysis of these frameworks is outside the scope of this preliminary inventory, it includes some of the principles of the GDPR, and the rights of data subjects that should be taken into account in the design and development of the CORTEX² framework.

3.5.1. **Social**

At this stage of the work done in WP4 “**Ethical and legal and social aspects**” and WP5 “**Architecture and use cases**”, we present the main identified psychological and social variables to be considered during the development phase of the CORTEX² applications. The identification of these variables was mainly guided by the interaction between the above work-packages as well as by a literature review. In the following months, studies will be conducted to

test the relevance of psychological and social variables in CORTEX² applications, keeping in mind that other variables could be identified during the development phase.

3.5.1.1 *Fatigue*

It refers to tiredness, anxiety or worry as a result of excessive use of virtual video conferencing platforms⁶, reelected by:

- Delay between a user action and the video conference that, although imperceptible, the brain “notices”.
- Lack of non-verbal communication by not seeing the whole person and not seeing for example his hands.
- Having an extended person talking to the user for a long time may be intimidating and threatening, even if he doesn't realize it.

Focusing on the case of video calls and training, the use of VR with a stage, full body, hand-tracking, and even some way to show emotions in the avatar would mitigate the second and third point by generating greater trust in your interlocutor^{7,8,9}. In the case of the first one, we can't think if there's anything we can do. In this case it should be noted that, according to previous studies, the higher the realism of the scene and the avatar, the greater the immersion and therefore the less fatigue¹⁰.

Although the use of virtual environments (VE) can reduce the level of fatigue related to video conferencing, it should be borne in mind that it can also increase it. Visual fatigue in VE is caused mainly by the vergence-accommodation conflict (VAC), or mismatch between perceived and

⁶ Wiederhold, B. K. (2020). Connecting through Technology during the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pandemic: Avoiding “zoom Fatigue.” *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*,

⁷ Kim, K., Boelling, L., Haesler, S., Bailenson, J., Bruder, G., & Welch, G. F. (2019). Does a Digital Assistant Need a Body? the Influence of Visual Embodiment and Social Behavior on the Perception of Intelligent Virtual Agents in AR. *Proceedings of the 2018 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality, ISMAR 2018*, 105–114.

⁸ Latoschik, M. E., Roth, D., Gall, D., Achenbach, J., Waltemate, T., & Botsch, M. (2017). The effect of avatar realism in immersive social virtual realities. *Proceedings of the ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology, VRST, Part F131944*.

⁹ van Loon, A., Bailenson, J., Zaki, J., Bostick, J., & Willer, R. (2018). Virtual reality perspective-taking increases cognitive empathy for specific others. *PLoS ONE*, 13(8), 1–19.

¹⁰ Weech, S., Kenny, S., & Barnett-Cowan, M. (2019). Presence and cybersickness in virtual reality are negatively related: A review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10(FEB), 1–19.

virtual depth. Another cause of fatigue is motion, especially vibrational motion experienced while using helmet mounted displays (HeMDs) while driving on rough terrains, as in military training. Motion sickness can be experienced in virtual environments whether due to visually moving backgrounds without physical movement (cybersickness) or due to simulated motion (simulator sickness) or bending the head out of the axis of the rotation of the visual background (optokinetic motion sickness)¹¹.

These variables that increase fatigue in VE are largely related to the presence in two senses. Since the greater the presence, the less fatigue is experienced, but the greater the variables that increase fatigue¹⁰. Therefore, getting a balance is very important. In addition, this level of fatigue will increase the longer the technology is used. So, it would be necessary to include a recommendation to take breaks every certain time of use, as is done in, for example, video games, where an alert appears when you have been using VR for a long time. Apart from the above, there are features to take into account that influence the fatigue independent of the software that will have to be taken into account¹²: age, gender, and personality. previous exhaustion and psychopathologies e.g., depression.

3.5.1.2 *Technostress*

Among the features of technology that have an impact on the technostress include technologies for video conferencing^{13,14}:

- Excess of notifications, ease of holding meetings and therefore excess of these during working hours and even outside of them. This requires further analysis to see if something can be done from our software beyond a recommendations section.

¹¹ Iskander, J., Hossny, M., & Nahavandi, S. (2018). A Review on Ocular Biomechanic Models for Assessing Visual Fatigue in Virtual Reality. *IEEE Access*, 6, 19345–19361.

¹² Montag, C., Rozgonjuk, D., Riedl, R., & Sindermann, C. (2022). On the associations between videoconference fatigue, burnout and depression including personality associations. *Journal of Affective Disorders Reports*, 10(April),

¹³ Baabdullah, A. M., Alsulaimani, A. A., Allamnakhrah, A., Alalwan, A. A., Dwivedi, Y. K., & Rana, N. P. (2022). Usage of augmented reality (AR) and development of e-learning outcomes: An empirical evaluation of students' e-learning experience. *Computers & Education*, 177, 104383.

¹⁴ Dragano, N., & Lunau, T. (2020). Technostress at work and mental health: concepts and research results. *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, 33(4), 407–413

- Fear that it will take too much effort, time, and cost to learn how to use the new software. It is necessary to ensure that the "training" of the software is adequate. In addition, it should be borne in mind that if the user is aware of the benefits of using technology, the level of technostress is reduced, so these benefits should be known by the user correctly, both before starting to use it and in the tutorial itself^{15,16}.

And some of them when using AR/VR specific with hyper-realistic avatars:

- Privacy issues due to the use of hyper-realistic avatars.
- A problem that arises from the use of hyperrealism to generate a complete avatar are the problems related to users not recognizing themselves in the avatar, not liking how they look, etc. Generating problems such as, insecurity in themselves when using the software¹⁷. This leads us to ask whether the generated avatar should be allowed to be modified and to what extent it should be allowed. But, being able to modify it also includes other possible problems, such as "body dysmorphia", where the user may develop other psychological pathologies due to the fact that the user may believe that his avatar has a better physical appearance than the one s/he really has. This point requires a deeper study since the studies consulted refer to a prolonged use of these avatars (video games and simulators).

Related to all the above, it is necessary to consider the immersion that the system must offer to generate an adequate "user presence". That is, the ability for the user to feel the virtual world as present and therefore be able to obtain the benefits expected from the use of this system. Initially, it can be understood that the higher the realism the greater immersion will be obtained. But studies agree that the tracking level (the system's ability to follow your movements), stereoscopy (depth of the scene) and the user's field of vision have a greater

¹⁵ Tarafdar, M., Pullins, E. B., & Ragu-Nathan, T. S. (2015). Technostress: Negative effect on performance and possible mitigations. *Information Systems Journal*, 25(2), 103–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/isj.12042>

¹⁶ Salo, M., Pirkkalainen, H., Eng Huang Chua, C., & Koskelainen, T. (2022). Formation and Mitigation of Technostress in the Personal Use of IT. *MIS Quarterly*, 46(2), 1073–1108

¹⁷ Thaler, A., Piryankova, I., Stefanucci, J. K., Pujades, S., de la Rosa, S., Streuber, S., Romero, J., Black, M. J., & Mohler, B. J. (2018). Visual perception and evaluation of photo-realistic self-avatars from 3D body scans in males and females. *Frontiers in ICT*, 5(SEP), 1–14.

impact than other characteristics such as image quality, resolution, and sound¹⁸. On the other hand, it must be considered that there are occasions (for example when there is a previous pathology such as social phobia or insecurities with your body) in which the user prefers less realism in these technologies¹⁹. Therefore, it is considered necessary to explore (maybe with a study) to compare the benefits and disadvantages of using hyperrealism versus realism.

3.5.2. Legal

The primary legal concern here is that Extended reality creates challenges for privacy, data protection the security for both the users of the technology and other bystanders whose data may be captured by the technology²⁰. There is also literature to support the growing concern around behavior manipulation in XR²¹. This is relevant for the CORTEX² framework because of the various data that will be processed, and the capabilities of the various AI components of the framework. Also, the insights that can be inferred as a result of the processing of user data, and possibly the data of other bystanders is a major concern. A spectrum of legal requirements and issues will be analyzed in the main deliverable for the legal and ethical inventory. However, for the design phase of CORTEX², there are some preliminary points to consider:

- I. The framework should ensure that users should be able to track data collection and be able to opt-in/out of such collection or processing with ease. The users need to be informed of the kind of data being collected by the various devices (wearable and non-wearable) used to access the framework.
- II. The XR solution should include security features to prevent cases of identity theft or impersonation that can lead to economic loss or loss of life²¹. For instance, the impersonation of a trainer/instructor at an industrial facility.
- III. Using XR technology exposes users to situations where inferences can be made about their lives, such as their mental state, sexual preferences and emotional state. Also, the

¹⁸ Cummings, J. J., & Bailenson, J. N. (2016). How Immersive Is Enough? A Meta-Analysis of the Effect of Immersive Technology on User Presence. *Media Psychology*, 19(2), 272–309.

¹⁹ Oh, C. S., Bailenson, J. N., & Welch, G. F. (2018). A systematic review of social presence: Definition, antecedents, and implications. *Frontiers Robotics AI*, 5(OCT), 1–35.

²⁰ Ellyse Dick, 'Balancing User Privacy and Innovation in Augmented and Virtual Reality' (Information Technology and Innovation Foundation 2021).

²¹ Melvin Abraham and others, 'Implications of XR on Privacy, Security and Behaviour: Insights from Experts', Nordic Human-Computer Interaction Conference (Association for Computing Machinery 2022)

data collected can be used for generating insights about conditions like autism, drug use, schizophrenia, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's and ADHD, all of which can lead to discrimination in the workplace²¹.

- IV. As noted, bystanders can also be affected by XR devices that capture visual, auditory and sensory information. Serious consideration should be given to how to prevent the violation of the privacy of bystanders.
- V. The avatars envisaged in CORTEX² are hyper-realistic and can be considered to be observable personal information, that could reveal sensitive information like race and gender. It is important to consider that some of the use cases might entail scenarios where users should be able to obfuscate their appearance or identity in order to protect their privacy. There could also be situations where users have legitimate reasons to like medical conditions such as vitiligo, or albinism. Will the avatars be recreated without allowing users to choose what they wish to disclose about themselves. CORTEX² should be designed in line with the GDPR to ensure that users still retain some level of autonomy and anonymity regarding their avatars.
- VI. It is important to consider the data minimisation principle of GDPR at the design stage to ensure that only data that is adequate, relevant and strictly necessary for the intended purposes of the CORTEX² framework is processed²².
- VII. In line with the storage limitation principle, and to ensure that the privacy of data subjects is preserved, it is important to know and indicate beforehand, before the commencement of processing activities, the typical data that will be stored by CORTEX² and the possible duration of such retentions²³. This is especially important given the ethical concerns regarding investigating the possible effects of the long-term use of XR.
- VIII. It is also pertinent to know beforehand what data is required for specific XR/AI components of the CORTEX² framework, as well as any insights/inferences that will be accessible to the various stakeholders (such as users or employers) in the course of processing activities in order to be able to think about the mitigations at the design stage.

²² Article 5(1)(c) GDPR

²³ Article (1)(e) GDPR

- IX. Under the GDPR, data subjects have a right to object to processing. It is important to consider how this requirement can be designed in line with the GDPR. It should be considered all interactions on the framework will be processed without the possibility for users to object to or voluntarily exclude certain interactions to protect their privacy.
- X. Given the several complex processing activities and outputs envisaged in the CORTEX² framework, it is pertinent to consider at the design stage the appropriate measures to ensure that there is a proper record of processing activities in line with the requirements of the GDPR²⁴. This is particularly important because the components of CORTEX² will be developed by different partners.

3.5.3. Ethical

The rise in the use of XR technology for uses other than entertainment has brought new dimensions of ethical concerns about immersive technologies. In light of this development, it is pertinent for the designers of the technologies to consider the long-term and wider repercussions of the technology and make certain to integrate ethics and moral sensitivity into the design of immersive technologies. Some of these ethical concerns are discussed below.

3.5.3.1 *Inclusiveness and Accessibility requirements*

In order to for new technology like XR not to reflect the existing social biases and power relations or worsen inequalities XR technologies must be designed in an inclusive manner²⁵. The workplace is not exempted from inequalities; hence it is pertinent to ensure that the design of digital collaborative workspaces like CORTEX² takes inclusiveness into account. For instance, in the design phase, it is pertinent to consider how the framework can accommodate users with a range of disabilities including auditory, cognitive, physical, neurological, visual and speech disabilities²⁵.

3.5.3.2 *User Safety*

There is a long history of harassment and user safety concerns in online spaces and this problem is gradually creeping into XR spaces that allow embodied interaction among users

²⁴ Article 30 GDPR

²⁵ Dylan Fox and Isabel Guenette Thornton, 'The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Extended Reality (XR) Ethics and Diversity, Inclusion, and Accessibility' [2022]

through the use of avatars in a virtual environment²⁶. These interactions create safety concerns about the physical and mental health of the users and involve a range of situations where some XR users create an unpleasant experience for other users, such as obscenities or derogatory comments made about an individual's race, religion, gender, sexual identity, nationality, or disability or other actions that make the Virtual environment less safe and inclusive for other users²⁶. Ethicists have argued that as the digital world expands through XR, there is a need to ensure that these digital spaces retain valuable elements of the physical world which underpin our social experiences²⁷. Anti-social behavior is still a menace in digital spaces including extended reality²⁸, and it is relevant for the project to consider how this framework can be designed in such a way that it can contribute to addressing/minimizing cases of harassment and antisocial behavior. To address some of these challenges, the CORTEX² project should consider implementing technical features to ensure the safety of users in the collaborative workspace. This includes features that enable users to make reasonable customization to their experiences and moderate their interactions in the virtual environment and escape or report such unpleasant and stressful incidents without interrupting or worsening their experience on the XR framework.

3.5.3.3 *Nudging*

Nudging remains an ethical issue with regard to new and emerging technologies like XR. Although research shows that nudging can be used to decrease work stress and improve work performance, it remains a threat to autonomy²⁹. Since the XR framework is imbued with AI capabilities like virtual assistants or chatbots, it is important to ensure that in designing the framework, the features that are meant to improve work performance and operational efficiency will not undermine the interest and autonomy of the users.

²⁶ Mangina and Eleni, 'The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report–Social and Multi-User Spaces in VR: Trolling, Harassment, and Online Safety' [2021]

²⁷ Andy Miah, 'The Moral Metaverse: Establishing an Ethical Foundation for XR Design', Understanding Virtual Reality (Routledge 2022).

²⁸ Laurence Morvan, Francis Hintermann, and Armen Ovanessoff, 'Preparing for the Risky World of Extended Reality' (2020) 61 MIT Sloan Management Review 1.

²⁹ Jared Weintraub, David Cassell, and Thomas P. DePatie, 'Nudging Flow through "SMART" Goal Setting to Decrease Stress, Increase Engagement, and Increase Performance at Work' (2021) 94 Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology 230

3.5.3.4 *Trust*

Another important ethical concern is how to harness the guidelines of Trustworthy AI- design in a way that benefits the users and mitigates issues surrounding fairness, algorithmic bias, transparency, and explainability of the CORTEX² framework. In the design of the framework, the four ethical principles highlighted by the EU High-level expert group on AI (HLEG AI) are: (1) The principle of human autonomy, (2) the principle of prevention of harm (3) The principle of fairness, and (4) The principle of explicability³⁰. These principles have been translated into specific requirements in the design and development of AI systems. The requirements include human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, Privacy and data governance, Transparency, Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, Societal and environmental well-being and Accountability³⁰. Achieving these values will require a range of technical and non-technical methods, and it is relevant to identify them in the design phase. These requirements for Trustworthy AI are similar to the requirements in the GDPR and the impending EU Artificial intelligence Act. For instance, it is necessary to establish beforehand, a pre-defined level of explainability in the CORTEX² project in order to comply with the transparency requirement.

3.5.4. **Data privacy and security requirements**

Security and privacy are two essential pillars in software development. Although these aspects are not the primary focus of this project, we have determined the minimal requirements to be fulfilled for the use of CORTEX² application, especially in terms of integration involving several heterogeneous components and those related to the interaction with IoT objects and the use of artificial intelligence models. We begin by quickly clarifying these notions before showing their relevance in CORTEX² framework development.

- **Data security** is the procedure in which it is made sure that data is protected from being accessed, manipulated, or corrupted by unauthorized personnel or applications during its span of life. It includes activities such as data encryption and hashing, multi-factor authentication, access control, breach response, network security or activity monitoring.

³⁰ Nathalie A. Smuha, 'The EU Approach to Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence' (2019)

- **Data integrity** or often also called data quality, indicates how consistent and untampered with a set of data is regardless of where and how it is stored. It ensures that data is accurate, reliable and available to authorized parties.
- **Data sovereignty** makes sure that your data is always subject only to the laws of the country which it is located in.
- **Data privacy** is concerned with proper handling, processing, storage and usage of personal data. According to the law, personal data means any information relating to an identified or identifiable individual; an identifiable person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identification number (e.g., social security number) or one or more factors specific to his physical, physiological, mental, economic, cultural or social identity (e.g., name and first name, date of birth, biometrics data, fingerprints, DNA...) (CNIL definition). Data privacy involved activities related to governing regulation and law application, policies and practices, data governance, third-party management such as cloud service providers

As CORTEX² will develop components but also integrate different third parties' services to build XR cooperative platforms., data privacy and data security are required on three sides:

- **Users:** Access control and data governance are needed to ensure that each user could only access to the data is authorized to. These users will also produce personal data that will be transmitted and stored. CORTEX² should handle this private data according to local regulation and dedicated policies.
- **CORTEX² components:** Some of the CORTEX² components will be directly impacted by data privacy and data security when interacting and exchanging data with other components.
- **Streams transmitted between CORTEX² devices:** Data stream use private and public network and contain personal information. In addition, some of them may be recorded or summarized. Hence, special care has to be taken to ensure data privacy and data security of this kind of data.

3.6. Requirements Analysis

The purpose of the analysis is to identify architecture components in terms of functionality, independent named units of code, from the requirements covered in Section 3.2 and establish the dependencies that could exist between them. Then, ask the question for each component if it will be developed on the client side only, server side only or both. On the basis of this analysis, it would then be easier to draw a high-level architecture diagram which would then allow to list the APIs and the inter-component interactions but also to assign responsibilities in terms of development, according to the skills and expertise of each partner. This analysis is summarized in Table 9, Table 10, Table 11, Table 12, Table 13 and Table 14 in the Annexes A, B, C and D.

3.7. Functionalities review regarding existing solutions

Collaborative work solutions already exist^{31,32}, like the simple fact of working on a document using Google docs or Microsoft teams until having a more complete environment, integrating chat functionalities, video conferencing and document sharing, as in the case of Twake, a product under constant development at LINAGORA.

In particular, tools for remote collaborative working are very present and offer more and more attractive features and already meet several needs of this project such as videoconferencing, chat. However, the CORTEX² project is not about new functionalities but about the way and the use of these features by including XR technologies and advances artificial intelligence in speech recognition and gesture detection. Below, we have compared the known state of the art solutions to the CORTEX² framework, once developed, to ensure that the needs expressed bring new opportunities for exploitation on the European and global market.

3.7.1. **Basic features**

These are features, that are generally found in almost all videoconferencing solutions, to allow a group of people to interact with each other through speech and text. The solutions, holding only these functionalities, can support a large number of people, as they do not require a large

³¹ iVIWE - Intelligent Virtual Immersive Work Environment, Alexandra Isabel Vieites Mendes, Faculdade de engenharia, universidade do Porto, September, 2021

³² Helios, 3D authoring tools for V-space creation, project deliverable 5.2, Dimitrios Ververidis et al. October 2021

amount of bandwidth or high performance on the client side. CORTEX² is not particularly interested in these features but for the project achievement, only a selection of features is retained to reach the objectives. However, CORTEX² takes into account the flexibility of development to leave the choice of expanding the CORTEX² framework to the exploitation plan of the pilots.

Table 4: Basic features comparison with existing solutions

Feature	Platforms								
	Skype	Zoom	Microsoft Teams	Google Meet	WebEx	Rainbow	Jitsi Meet	Mozilla Hubs	CORTEX ²
Screen Sharing	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
File Sharing	X	X	X	X	X	X	None	X	X
Chat Function	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Group & Private Messaging	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Audio-Only Conferencing	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Call Recording	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	None	X
Unlimited Number of Meetings	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Contact Channels (Chat groups)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

3.7.2. Visual features

These features bring more usability to collaborative applications to ensure a better user experience but they do not improve the cooperation. The exchange remains at the same level as described in the section above with more performance solicitation in the client and server sides. CORTEX² pays a lot of attention to the visual aspects but in the sense to enhance the cooperation not in terms of user informal communications, for example, accessing a better 3D view of a real objects to allow a better diagnosis.

Table 5: Visual features comparison with existing solutions

Feature	Platforms
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	Skype	Zoom	Microsoft Teams	Google Meet	WebEx	Rainbow	Jitsi Meet	Mozilla Hubs	CORTEX ²
Audio and Video HD Call	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Video and Audio Preview Screen	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	None	None
Background Effects	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	None
Touch Up my Appearance	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Together Mode	X	X	X	X	None	None	None	None	None
Spotlight Speaker	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	None	None
Mosaic of videos	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	None	None
Face Filters	X	X	X	X	X	None	X	X	X

3.7.3. Useful and interactive addition

Collaborative work in this case takes advantage of new features such as whiteboard, voice technology and use of artificial intelligence. These features require a lot of bandwidth and demand a lot of performance on the client and server sides. Therefore, only a few features are supported in a single application. The impact on cooperation is improved by allowing teams to better understand each other when sharing information or working on a common concept.

Table 6: Interaction features comparison with existing solutions

Feature	Platforms								
	Skype	Zoom	Microsoft Teams	Google Meet	WebEx	Rainbow	Jitsi Meet	Mozilla Hubs	CORTEX ²
Virtual Hand Raising	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Polling	X	X	X	X	X	None	X	None	None
Interactive Whiteboard	X	X	X	X	X	None	X	None	None
Messaging	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Live Subtitles/Translation	X	X	X	X	X	None	None	None	X

Chat Translation	X	X	X	X	X	None	None	None	None
Search Chat	X	X	X	X	X	X	None	None	None
Speech to Text	None	None	X	X	None	None	None	None	X
Meeting summarization	None	X							
Interactive document editing	X	X	X	X	X	None	None	None	None

3.7.4. XR Features

XR features for collaboration are new. They are highly consumer of hardware resources and require dictated devices for users. Efforts are currently underway to develop cooperative solutions for XR environment such as Microsoft XXX and Mozilla hub. However, gaming and entertainment take over, the market still needs XR cooperation facilities. CORTEX² fills this gap and opens a new perspective to the use of XR for collaboration by planning to develop the functionalities below.

Table 7: Extended XR features comparison with existing solutions

Feature	Platforms								
	Skype	Zoom	Microsoft Teams	Google Meet	WebEx	Rainbow	Jitsi Meet	Mozilla Hubs	CORTEX ²
3D Avatar	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	X	X
Object recognition	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	X
3D scene	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	X	X
Real Object scanning	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	x
Hand Superposition	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	X
Virtual presence	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	X	X
Virtual IoT actuation	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	X
Virtual assistant	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	None	X

Pose tracking	None	X							
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4. High level Architecture

Following the requirement analysis, we derive a high-level architecture to have a clear view of the platform components and to synthesize the project needs in terms of development presented in the previous parts of this document. It will be the reference for the future implementation of the different modules and their interaction and will be detailed in the second version of this deliverable D5.5 “**CORTEX² requirements and deployment architecture**” at M34.

The high-level architecture of the platform is described in three layers of Figure 5: the Cortex **Client** block that will work on the client side, the Cortex Core block that will work on the infrastructure or cloud side and the Third-party block that represents partner functionalities provided as a service, i.e., deployed in an external infrastructure. The following sections provide detailed information about each of the individual components that make up the CORTEX² solution.

Figure 5: The CORTEX² high-level architecture

4.1. CORTEX Client components

A CORTEX² application can have several views according to the role that the user can take. We can notice that especially for an industrial use case and a learning use case, different types of

users are involved in the same application but have different views depending on the role they play in the cooperation.

The components of Figure 6 will be developed to run on the XR device, laptop or smart phone in order to provide the user with the appropriate interface for his application. They are very dependent on the application domain. It is not planned to develop an authoring tool i.e., an application generator, because it could take us away from the scope of this project and it is very resource intensive. Each application may have to use only a part of these components because the user views, for the same application, could be very different, and some components may not be necessary for another type of application. There are three pilots that could exploit differently such components. This topic is widely discussed in task T2.1 “**Abstract multi-view collaborative space model**” and T2.2. “**AR/VR Behaviour and intention modelling**”. We will also point this need as a goal for the remainder of this project to help facilitate the composition of applications based, for example, on Node-Red³³. The brief description of each component is given below:

Figure 6: Architecture of the CORTEX² Client

- **Application scenario life cycle** is the heart component of CORTEX² APP. it manages the life cycle of the application by invoking the functionalities provided by other elements of the architecture.
- **Cortex authentication** is used for access management, user role and profile.

³³ <https://nodered.org/>

- **Cortex scene, objects and persona** is managing the different participants avatars and scene representation.
- **Scene changes tracking and update** shares authorized changes or events in a scene between the different participants, for example, if an object is moved by a user A, this might impact the rendering of user B application.
- **Application 3D/2D scene assists** are providing necessary objects needed to the construction of scene. Some predefined objects and scenes are stored in the Cortex core Database to allow quick starting of a Cortex app.
- **Cortex Rainbow SDK media and data transport** is used to connect to the core components and data transportation including the different media.
- **Cortex speech prefabs** is managing advanced conversational features and allow voice interaction to use within the rendering framework and targeted-devices. For meeting summarization, users with an organisational role should authenticate to the conversational manager service³⁴ provided by LINAGORA to review the auto-generated summary.
- **Cortex IoT SDK** provides the end-user applications with the libraries/mechanisms required to enable the access to and interaction with the IoT objects, either from the Cortex Core components or directly from the uiTOP platform³⁵, provided by ICOM uiTOP platform may have to integrate with the Cortex Core authentication mechanisms in order to handle users' access rights to IoT objects. The Cortex IoT SDK participates in the translation of the end user VR/AR "language" to an internal IoT format, readable by the Cortex Core or the uiTOP.

4.2. Core components

Core-components group architectural elements that have a similar role or are highly dependent on each other. They are detached from external services to differentiate what will be developed from the existing ones and to facilitate the architecture understanding. Two core components are identified and presented in Figure 7. They are detailed in the following sections.

³⁴ <https://convos.linto.ai/login>

³⁵ https://www.intracom-telecom.com/en/products/telco_software/loT/loT_orchestration_Platform.htm

Figure 7: Architecture of the CORTEX² Core Components

4.2.1. Rainbow Core

Rainbow-core³⁶, provided by Alcatel Lucent Enterprise, is dedicated to connectivity and media transportation through its available SDK in the client side. Rainbow-core supports user authentication access using email and password, or the delegation of authority. It also includes the capability of collaboration and conferencing within “bubbles”, which are setup and monitored through the Rainbow SDK. Rainbow-core handles all communication channels for data exchange between participants in the collaborative room. It is also in charge of transporting medias, signalization and metadata to the right Mediation Gateway connected the XR services modules.

4.2.2. Cortex Core

Cortex-core brings together a set of components that are identified from the requirements and will be developed for the project purpose. They have the specificity to belong to the same deployment infrastructure, unlike some services that will be developed and deployed outside the cortex core environment.

- **Cortex-DB** is used for data persistence including 3D models, speech recognition data, users' profiles, IoT objects information, etc.

³⁶ <https://developers.openrainbow.com/>

- **Management core** is made up of three components. They provide a set of utilities for user's and IoT registration, role management and authorizations. End-users' authentication is done through Rainbow SDK. It also allows the management and provision of media streams and other data in the platform. Particularly, IoT device management connects IoT world to Cortex XR world by giving access to associated sensors data or actuators. There is no generic administration GUI and it has to be considered according to pilots' usage.
- **Scene synchronization** is used to align scenes views across multiple shared virtual (or augmented) user environment. The synchronization will be achieved via data and events routing relaying on Cortex App components (Scene changes tracking and update, Cortex Rainbow SDK media and data transport) and Rainbow core.
- **IoT Scene synchronization** has the same goal as the previous element but with sharing restrictions taking into account the user's preferences and, security and privacy reasons. In case an IoT object is visible and usable by to other users, then actions or sensors status should be synchronized across users' scenes. Regarding IoT integration, uiTOP platform may be accessed either directly from the end-user application or through the Cortex core server components, also taking into account whether the information from the actuation/sensor needs to be shared or not.
- **Cortex Mediation Gateway** handles the routing of medias and metadata to the most appropriated XR and speech technologies services.
- **Rainbow-SDK** is a Rainbow Core Client simplifying the API access and management to the **Rainbow Core** APIs.
- **Mediation Gateway Remote Orchestration** is a component responsible of routing calls to external services from the Cortex Mediation Gateway.

4.3. Cortex services

Cortex services are big code pieces, provided as services and deployed outside the platform to facilitate integration. Incoming or outgoing media data, to these services, is driven by the Cortex Mediation Gateway via the Rainbow Core media server.

Identified services from the requirements are represented in Figure 8 and are described in the following. They will be released faster because the responsibility of their development is already

resolved and they do not require the intervention of additional partners. The API will be explicitly defined in task 5.2 “**XR Architecture design and deployment**”

Figure 8: Set of the CORTEX² Services

- **Video Compression/Alternative Appearance service** is used to save bandwidth when multiple users participate to the virtual cooperation environment. Instead of the transmitting 2D video, only metadata, low-dimension representation, is transmitted. DFKI will provide the encoder/decoder component.
- **Gesture Interaction service** reproduces hand poses from real user gestures and makes them available for a virtual interaction with real objects.
- **Instant 3D models service** implements and provides necessary APIs for AR scene analysis and objects recognition.
- **Voice Transcription service** provides live speech to text technology for different languages.
- **Virtual Assistant/Conversational Agent service** provides design patterns to handle live interaction between a user and the Cortex app or a user and the virtual assistant in cooperation environment.
- **Document Summarization service** is used to extract summaries from written documents, saved as files or stored in databases.
- **Meeting Summarization service** implements and provides discourse summarization API. In addition, a conversational tool will be made available to extend the generated summaries with annotation and NLP based tasks.
- **Cortex IoT server** is based on ICOM's uiTOP platform to implement and provide the necessary APIs for the management of IoT objects and their data including IoT objects

registration/connectivity, monitoring/measurements, as well as actuation. The relevant flow goes through the Cortex core components.

4.4. CORTEX² data privacy and security

To meet this need, we started establishing some rules and identifying possible risks, according to requirement of Section 3.2, then applying them to the different components that have been presented above. Data privacy and security rules concern mainly four points, below while Table 8 lists all the components which will require specific handling to ensure data privacy and security.

1. **Access control and authentication:** CORTEX² will provide access control through simple login/pwd authentication. Access will grant various rights to the users depending on its role declared in the platform.
2. **Encryption:** Streams and other data should be protected from reading and modification through encryption. State of the art encryption such as ssh or SRTP protocols will be used as already part of WebRTC and web design best practices. Transport encryption is used to protect all connections to and from the Service and between participants.
3. **Data integrity:** CORTEX² will rely on the technologies and the policies of the Cloud service provider which will be used to host and run CORTEX² platform. Cortex core will be deployed on the OVHcloud GDPR-compliant cloud service infrastructure in Europe. These data centres rely on modern ISO-27001 and SOC certified technologies, isolation with barbed-wire fences and where physical access is strictly monitored 24×7. They also ensure data redundancy and data synchronization.
4. **Data privacy:** Cortex services will be designed to be compliant with European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). CORTEX² framework will leverage Rainbow component compliancy with RGPD. Rainbow is at the core of CORTEX² framework and will handle media distribution. It will also include processes to ensure GDPR compliance for the whole framework, paying attention to the risks on data privacy brought by new components such as the CORTEX² database, the IoT platform, the mediation gateway and the 3 management modules.

Table 8: List of components with specific privacy/security handling

Component	Types of risk	Data privacy	Data security
IoT platform	DoS, data modification, data steal	x	x
Cortex DB	Data steal, data loss, data modification	x	x
Rainbow SDK	Unauthorized access,	None	x
User Management	User impersonation, unauthorized access	None	x
IoT device Management	Unauthorized access, eavesdropping	None	x
Data management	Unauthorized access, data steal or modification	x	x
Cortex SDK	Unauthorized access	None	x
Mediation gateway	Eavesdropping,	None	x
AI models	Used for system infiltration, retrieve original data	x	x

4.5. Expected deployment infrastructure

To ensure global WAN availability of the solution worldwide, the Cortex core components will be deployed, according to each scenario constraints, under the **Alcatel-Lucent-Enterprise Kubernetes cluster**. Kubernetes environment simplifies the deployment process of the software solution and offers sufficient flexibility to ensure high availability and scalability within a continuous delivery. **Alcatel-Lucent-Enterprise Kubernetes instances** are located in Europe and managed by Alcatel-Lucent Enterprise team. The servers are hosted on a sovereign provider. Each component will be run in Docker containers to ensure isolation and integration facilities. It is deployed using **Helm**³⁷ chart definitions for each scenario. If during the integration process, there are services or components that require more computing power, other Kubernetes nodes or external servers with GPU capabilities will be leased. The end user application binaries will be also accessible through a dedicated storage hosted at Kubernetes side.

³⁷ <https://helm.sh/>

To succeed in this deployment, each partner, in charge of the development, will provide a clear description of the variables associated to its component and its dependencies. If the component is part of the Cortex core, then a docker image is required or its source code should be available in CORTEX² Gitlab repository. Being in charge of the deployment, Alcatel-Lucent Enterprise will manage through **Helm** the definition of the different packages according to the components provided by the partners. The definition will be, as most as possible, generic to support the 3 use cases deployment.

Besides, a continuous integration, based on the tool **Flux**³⁸ will be setup to manage both the deployment during the development and the integration phase, but also in the production context. The CI/CD process is based on Git repository. CORTEX² Group is already created in the GitLab instance hosted by DFKI and the different components to be integrated into the CORTEX² Framework will have to be delivered at least 2 weeks before the build and deployment of a new iteration.

5. Identified implementation approaches

We rely on two existing authoring tools Unity3D and Mozilla Hubs to ease the developers in CORTEX² specific modules integration within a 3D application. Unity Editor is bringing all what we need for CORTEX² from 3D scene construction and animation point of view and for integrators/developers that makes it easy for them to enter quickly and efficiently in the proposed CORTEX² framework. Opensource approach is based on Mozilla Hubs integration as it is a main player in the open source metaverse. We identified Mozilla Hubs fits with the Business meeting pilot requirements.

5.1. Unity

Unity is a Cross-platform game engine. It allows to develop within an integrated development environment as whereas games or industrial application on a variety of desktop, mobile, console and virtual reality platforms such as XR or AR headsets. Unity is one of the most popular development tools for such cases. In the context of CORTEX², the capability to address most of

³⁸ <https://github.com/fluxio>

all Virtual Reality device with an easy developer adoption made us select Unity for the project. Unity will help to develop all client's component, from the 3D environment definition, to the media integration and interactions. Unity is not open source and may be a barrier to some developers but its XR capabilities are unavoidable and may be a motivation for more advanced Cortex-based development. Therefore, to support Unity environment, a dedicated Rainbow SDK for Unity package will be developed over the existing Rainbow C# SDK.

5.2. Mozilla hub

Mozilla Hubs is powered by Mozilla Mixed Reality – the XR arm of one of the world's leading browser technology providers. The company launched Mozilla Hubs in 2018, as a free, experimental software that'd help users from different industries and verticals try out VR collaboration as an alternative to traditional conferencing tools. Hubs became so popular that in 2020, Mozilla launched a paid option for enterprises hosted on the cloud. The new Mozilla Hubs cloud is based on Amazon Web Services (AWS), meanwhile, Hubs continues to be an open-source project, available on GitHub for anyone to customise and use. Mozilla Hubs is built as an open environment to host a virtual event such as a museum or digital gallery, open a classroom and team meeting. However, leaving it too open makes it difficult to include new features because they have to be adapted to different types of applications. Thus, one way to exploit Mozilla Hubs is to customize it or to reuse some parts in order to have an application dedicated to a given domain that can be extended by high level functionalities that improve the exploitation of the application for such domain. These features are for example automatic speech recognition, virtual assistant, gesture recognition, intention recognition and many others that are currently not fully available.

Mozilla Hubs itself is based on open-source tools that we wish to be inspired, reused or partially customized some parts for the needs of this project. We agree with the idea that the metaverse could follow this same path as the Web³⁹. The web was a small set of protocols and software that led to the explosive growth of the network that became the Internet. Both the web and the internet are growing exponentially for example integration of IoT objects, increasingly powerful browsers and cloud computing. The metaverse is the next step of this evolution process.

³⁹ <https://gfodor.medium.com/the-secret-mozilla-hubs-master-plan-2c1364033bec>

The browser will be the support of Pilot3 application, running in different devices. Pilot3 will interface with the Rainbow legacy videoconferencing solution in order to show the ability to marry the XR with existing ones ensuring heterogeneity across different technologies and allowing a large set of users to softly turned to the metaverse, currently unavailable for all.

6. Provisional development timeline

The development workflow is organized into milestones, managed by the task T5.2 “**CORTEX² architecture design, integration and deployment**”, where each one corresponds to a running version of the extended Rainbow platform using CORTEX² framework. After discussion between partners and in view of the expressed requirements, the planning on the proposal seems reasonable unless unexpected events occur. The team has agreed to act quickly by informing any new change. So, the roadmap can be adjusted.

A minimal viable version is configured by M12. Then, CORTEX² components are implemented and integrated gradually to the platform by M18, M24 and M30. At M12, only a basic MVP version of CORTEX² will be available implementing primary components of the HLA among them: Unity Rainbow plug-in to allow application connectivity to the Rainbow Core and a POC that demonstrates the integration of the Mediation Gateway and the VCAA XR service. In addition, a first implementation of Cortex Core Management components will have also to be in place by M12. Then, Pilots implementation starts at M13. They will focus on the integration of extended reality modules and services depending to each use case. We will adapt our agility to the global pace of the different pilots to decide how many intermediate iterations will occur while keeping the key Milestones in mind.

7. Requirements assessment procedures

The evaluation criteria are defined to allow quantitative methods or ranking. Without these, the project team will not know if the requirements were sufficient to reach the objectives and consequently act more quickly if there exit a lack in the initial specification.

The requirements have made it possible to identify a list of components. To ensure that the true needs are identified, justifiable, and clearly articulated, the idea is to follow the development progress in percent. The percent will be assigned by each pilot. It determines the ability of a component to meet the needs of the pilot. For example, if pilot 3 approves the

component X as having met all its needs, this is equivalent to 33%, 50% or 100% depending on the number of pilots having used this component. To improve this procedure, we will judge each component of CORTEX² framework by the number of times it has been used by 3rd parties. For example, if we had to improve a component 5 times to meet 3 extra requirements, the component becomes more complete and therefore, its contribution to the project is stronger by 15/100.

The status of this progress will act as an indicator of the components being integrated and their ability to handle emergencies, for example, the incapacity of a component to respond to a requirement due to a misunderstanding or a wrong selection.

8. Conclusion

In this deliverable, we addressed the definition of the use cases of the CORTEX² framework and the identified requirements. First, we provided an in-depth description of the pilots by specifying the functional and non-functional requirements of the framework starting from the use cases. In order not to freeze the use domain around the pilots, we consider CORTEX² as a framework that will allow different possible combinations and usages of CORTEX² components, which will allow for the development of additional cooperative applications through 3rd parties who will be recruited during the FSTP calls. After having successfully identified a list of components from the requirements, we designed CORTEX² high level architecture to be used for the precise description of the modules, their interfaces, and their implementation.

In this deliverable, we have also extended the requirements to cover all issues around the development of the project such as social, legal and ethical needs, expectation from the FSTP calls, provisional developments plan, and hardware specification to identify possible constraints.

This work will allow for the start of the prototyping phase, in which the different modules will be further specified and implemented, with the objective of delivering a Minimum Viable Product at the planned milestone in Month 12.

9. Annex A: Table of Functional Requirements

The following table lists the identified functional requirements

Table 9: Functional requirements

ID	Pilot	Description	Rationale	Priority	Elicited By
<i>Unique identifier</i>	<i>P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot, P2: Remote Training Pilot, P3: Business Meeting Pilot</i>	<i>High level process, function or capability that the requirement addresses.</i>	<i>Why is this requirement needed?</i>	<i>Priority of this requirement: Mandatory Desirable Optional</i>	<i>Who captured the requirement?</i>
UC1V1R11	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be able to receive participant videos	to convert them thanks to "avatarization" service to biometrics hot points and be able to sent back those element in order to improve client side rendering on a low bandwidth connection	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R12	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be able to generate a report at the end of a live session	to get an executive summary, with date, subject, names of participants with a discussion transcript will be made followed by a notification to all participants.	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL

UC1V1R15	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands or by processing action on personal IoT devices (wearables) or virtual objects/entities	to start XR modules interaction	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R16	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to join the collaboration room with his head-mounted display (VR or AR glasses)	to start the conference	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R17	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to initiate audio /video recording	to archive the recording	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R18	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to select the several files, drawing or message to display on his device	to get assistance in issue solving	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R19	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to take snapshots, annotate them	to share them to the collaboration room and for reporting	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R20	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to interact with IoT devices	to request an action or to retrieve some information	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R21	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to share his XR device rendering with or without AR overlay	to let the remote expert see really what he see	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL

UC1V1R22	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to interact with IoT devices	to request an action or to retrieve some information	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R29	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician wants to receive enhanced AR overlay	to get more support during issue resolution	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R42	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician should be able to perform a rapid scan of the industrial machine to produce a virtual model of his environment (as a textured mesh or point cloud)	To send the model to the experts	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC1V1R43	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The virtual model of the industrial machine should be matched with a set of existing models	To identify the actual machine	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC1V1R44	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	Annotations made by the expert on the virtual model should appear in AR mode in the view of the technician	To visualize the expert indication in AR mode	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC1V1R45	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician should have the possibility to "erase" the annotations when he understood the situation	To clean up annotations	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC1V1R46	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	Actions on the physical machine should produce a visual feedback in AR mode when the machine is connected as an IoT device	To provide a visual feedback of actions	01-Mandatory	DFKI

UC1V1R47	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	Movements of the hand of the expert should be visible as virtual hands in the view of the technician	To provide a visual feedback of actions	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC1V1R49	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The IoT platform must be able to detect critical issues in the industrial operation and notify the CORTEX platform.	To initiate the intervention procedure	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC1V1R50	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The IoT platform must be able to extract information about the context of the industrial breakdown from the IoT devices/sensors and forward it to the CORTEX platform.	To initiate the intervention procedure	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC1V1R51	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	IoT Devices/sensors of heterogeneous IoT protocols (e.g. WiFi) must be supported by the system.	To cover the range of information required for the industrial operation	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC1V1R52	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The stakeholders must be able to attend the collaborative meeting using one or more devices among a variety of AR or legacy devices supported by the system e.g. computer with camera, cellphone, MR glasses.	To support seamless integration between legacy and XR platforms	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC1V2R01	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The expert should be able to visualize the rendering of the environment of the technician	To understand the situation	01-Mandatory	DFKI

UC1V2R01	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As machine expert, I want to , thanks to voice assistant, request a document search by giving keywords,	to extract all relevant documents by order or relevance and provide a link for a direct access to the right part of the document to consider as well as with a small extract of this content. to select the several files, drawing or messages to display on technician interface	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V2R02	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The expert should be able to navigate or "manipulate" the 3D model to position it as required	To ease the interaction with the model	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC1V2R02	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As machine expert, I want to be able to see on my screens a reconstructed scene previously sent by a technician	to be able to record with my hands so actions to reproduce at technician side and, as an option, having the possibility for Slow motion reconstruction of the field expert moves	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V2R03	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The expert should be able to annotate the 3D model with different tools (paintbrush, arrows, circles)	To explain the situation visually	01-Mandatory	DFKI

UC1V2R03	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As machine expert, I want to be able to capture my hand gestures	to have a mix rendering between my hand and a reconstruction model	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V2R04	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The expert should be able to use his/her hands to show something to the technician	To explain the situation in real time	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC1V2R04	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As machine expert, I want to be able to capture my hand gestures	so that technician and customer could see depending of their devices, either a mixed reality or a full mixed reconstructed video.	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V3R01	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As collaboration room participant, I want to be able to reconstruct picture and lip movement on my device side	to improve and lower by bandwidth consumption	01-Mandatory	ALCATEL
UC1V1R08	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be able to text analyse past tickets	to identify a short list of experts	02-Optional	ALCATEL
UC1V1R13	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be able to atomically dig into database the previously cases	to get a previous session playback and to navigate in it thru hot words	02-Optional	ALCATEL
UC1V1R26	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to playback an archived record		02-Optional	ALCATEL

UC1V2R05	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As machine expert, I want to be able to capture my hand gestures	so that a short loop of the gesture is reproduced live on glasses to explain the gesture to apply	02-Optional	ALCATEL
UC1V3R04	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As Customer, Decision maker, I want to be able to use biometry or 2FA	so that, I will be able to secure the legal value of a decision for future consultation	02-Optional	ALCATEL
UC1V1R01	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use a visual authentication method for the headset (ex: QR code to link the device to the right user)	to simplify headset pairing and allow a simple attribution and login	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R03	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The administrator can register the list of technician and associated information (expertise, location, ...),	to contact the right experts according the issue	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R04	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The administrator can register the list of machine expert and associated information (expertise, type of machine, ...)	to contact them in case of expertise needs	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R05	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The administrator can register the customer/ decision maker and associated information (site, ...)	to contact them in case of decision needs	03-Desirable	ALCATEL

UC1V1R06	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be able to be triggered for a case creation	to first create the collaboration room and then add the technician(s) as participant, attached the case related files, and send a notification with urgency level is send to the collaboration room	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R07	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be interconnected with an IoT platform	to extract sensors informations from issued machine	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R09	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be able to request the initial configuration snapshot of an industrial machine	to compare it to current configuration snapshot	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R10	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The system shall be able to take and store participant pictures	to locally (on participant devices) animate them (lips,...) in synchronization with the incoming voice	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R14	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The IoT platform shall be able to do health analysis of industrial process according to tailored programmed scenarios	to detect critical issues and send alerts	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R23	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to add the best available expert to assist me on a case	to get the best assistance	03-Desirable	ALCATEL

UC1V1R24	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to request the system for the configuration modifications associated to a machine and to get the rendering on his headset device.	to request an action or to retrieve some information	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R25	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can use "hot words" commands to perform media control	to mute/unmute the mic ...	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R27	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can activate voice noise (glasses side or cloud side)	remote participants would be able to ear the technician more clearly	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R28	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician can take a scene snapshot on demand, request a validation	Cortex will be able to do a modelisation for a later reconstruction at machine expert side	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R30	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician wants to be able to take personal vocal notes or to interact with a vocal assistant		03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC1V1R48	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	The technician should be able to view the head of the expert in a video mode (floating window near the industrial machine)	To see the expert while workin	03-Desirable	DFKI
UC1V3R02	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As Customer, Decision maker, I want to be notified with alert in case of lot platform issues	so that, I will be able to join the crisis room	03-Desirable	ALCATEL

UC1V3R03	P1: Industrial Maintenance Pilot	As Customer, Decision maker, I want to be notified with alert in case of lot platform issues	so that, I will be able to see, the resolution progress thanks to textual summaries resulting of other participant speech transcript.	03-Desirable	ALCATEL
UC2S1R12	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can communicate with audio and video through the Rainbow platform	To transmit the instruction to the trainees	01-Mandatory	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R13	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can do group calls with trainee(s)	To exchange simultaneously the multiple trainees	01-Mandatory	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R14	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can send commands to trainee VR devices	he can manage lesson starting, choose the right lesson to load for the right trainee	01-Mandatory	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R21	P2: Remote Training Pilot	For training cognitive skills, a 3D model of the situation to train on should be provided to the trainee	Training should be done in a environment that is as near as possible to the real situation	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC2S1R21	P2: Remote Training Pilot	For training a skill that depends on the actual real environment, an AR mode should be enabled, in which the trainee sees his real environment and the additional objects in Augmented Reality	Training should be done in a environment that is as near as possible to the real situation	01-Mandatory	DFKI
UC2S1R10	P2: Remote Training Pilot	A trainee can send voice messages in the chat to their trainer	to offer an easy way of asynchronous communication	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE

			between the student and the teacher		
UC2S1R17	P2: Remote Training Pilot		he can evaluate the quality and offer the adapted support	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R19	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can have his 3D avatar visible within the 3D scene	trainees would be able to see him when he is present in a current lesson session	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R20	P2: Remote Training Pilot	For training manual skills, a replicate of the object to train on should be connected as IoT device	Manual skills training should be trained with physical feedback (force feedback)	02-Optional	DFKI
UC2S1R8	P2: Remote Training Pilot	If the trainee raises their hand, a notification for the trainer is triggered	to notify the trainer in case of questions	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R9	P2: Remote Training Pilot	A trainee can record and take notes during a lesson	to support learning after the lesson	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R10	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The participants must be able to attend the remote business meeting using one or more devices among a variety of VR/AR or legacy devices supported by the system e.g. laptop, VR glasses.	To support seamless integration between legacy and XR platforms	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC2S1R11	P2: Remote Training Pilot	IoT Devices/sensors of heterogeneous IoT protocols (e.g. WiFi) to be supported by the system.	To cover the range of potential training requirements	02-Optional	ICOM

UC2S1R12	P2: Remote Training Pilot	IoT Devices should give notifications to user regarding events during his training (e.g. alarms).	To facilitate the learning process	02-Optional	ICOM
UC2S2R2	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can switch from a trainee's session to another in "breakout" context	To manage multi trainees' sessions and to easily react to hand rising	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S2R3	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can exchange with chat with other participants	To send instructions	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S2R6	P2: Remote Training Pilot	A trainee in a multiple-trainee lesson can be represented as a 3D avatar and interact with other participants' avatars	to enable virtual interaction between participants	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S2R7	P2: Remote Training Pilot	A trainee in a multiple-trainee lesson can switch breakout session	to talk to other groups of participants or train on a specific training goal	02-Optional	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R11	P2: Remote Training Pilot	A trainee can use keywords as voice commands on their VR device	to request cortex services (cortex actions)	03-Desirable	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R15	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can configure the experience of the trainees	he can change the training settings	03-Desirable	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R16	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can share their PC screen	all participants would be able to saw my presentation in a dedicated virtual screen under the VR environment	03-Desirable	ACTIMAGE

UC2S1R7	P2: Remote Training Pilot	A trainee is automatically muted on his device when he logs in to the call with another device, e.g. a VR headset	to avoid acoustic feedback loops that disturb the lesson	03-Desirable	ACTIMAGE
UC2S2R5	P2: Remote Training Pilot	A trainee in a multiple-trainee lesson can participate in lessons with several other participants with all of them seeing the same 3D scene, audio, avatars and screen shares	to provide the same information to all participants	03-Desirable	ACTIMAGE
UC2S1R18	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can navigate as remote view under a 3D scene received as video stream	To show the scene from a preferred/different point of view, To show the scene without rendering, share his point of view with other participant		ACTIMAGE
UC2S2R1	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Trainer can create lesson's modules and store lesson's contents	To precharge contents or download it on demand from trainee's devices and started automatically once ready		ACTIMAGE
UC2S2R4	P2: Remote Training Pilot	The Supervisor can receive audio and video streams from active training	To monitor the progress of such training without participating myself		ACTIMAGE
UC3P1R01	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow users (meeting organizer) to log into their account by entering their email and password.	Only by registered users can use Cortex2 application	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA

UC3P1R03	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow the user (organizer of the meeting) to create a XR business meeting room.	in order to set up the XR environment and choose the features to be used for this meeting (especially to preserve bandwidth)	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P1R04	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex should allow organizer of the meeting to register a name and access link for a given XR meeting room	to have a reference to the room	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P1R06	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 user (organizer of the meeting) to choose an environment for the meeting room	To increase usability	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P1R07	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Meeting organizer must be able to add, drop XR objects and personalize it business meeting environment	To increase usability	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P1R08	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Meeting organizer should have rights to enable or disable features allowed in business meeting environment	To increase usability	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P1R08	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should provide a default configuration and functionalities for XR business meeting room	for users who do not have a deep experience with the platform	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P1R10	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As an organizer, I want to be able to activate a virtual assistant participant	The virtual assistant is not 01-Mandatory. Thus the organizer must be able to disable it	01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P1R11	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As an virtual assistant, I want to access participants agenda	This will allow to setup future meetings on request.	01-Mandatory	CEA

UC3P1R12	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a participant, I want to allow or deny access to my agenda to other (virtual) participants		01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P1R13	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As an organizer, I want to share documents with participants		01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P2R02	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should be able to process connexion from different legacy(rainbow) and XR devices	To be able participating to a meeting	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R03	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should be able to adapt the rendering of the collaborative environment to user device	To be able participating to a meeting	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R04	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow the user (meeting participants) to choose or create its avatar at room meeting login	To have a reference to the participant	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R05	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow the synchronization between XR business meeting room of each participant	to avoid conflicting collaborative usage	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R06	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting participant should be able to start a conversation call with other perons in the meeting	To be able participating to a meeting	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R07	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting participant should be able to start a screen sharing in the meeting	To be able presenting some thing	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA

UC3P2R08	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting participant should be able to share a video in the meeting	To be able showing some thing	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R09	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting participant should be able to start chatting with other participating persons	To be able to discuss	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R11	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting Organiser should be able to generate meeting report (i.e., minutes)	To produce Minutes of the meeting automatically	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R12	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Busness meeting participant should be able to monitor his mobile from XR business meeting	To be able handling any urgency	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R13	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting participant should be able to change his status to temporary absent	To be able handling any urgency	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R16	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The avatar of a participant should disappear if the participant leave the room (its status changes)	To keep coherence accross the platform	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R17	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The avatar of a participant should be able to rise hand	To keep coherence accross the platform	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P2R22	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	A participant should be able to appear as a virtual avatar, or as a video stream represented in the 3D scene as a billboard		01-Mandatory	DFKI

UC3P2R24	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The system should be able to dynamically discover and register the various IoT devices and make them available to the users.	To automate the process	02-Optional	ICOM
UC3P2R25	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The system should offer IoT analytics and render IoT information as AR annotations over video streams.	To enable VR/AR experience	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC3P2R26	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	An IoT device should offer the capability to be removed/updated where needed.	To recover from potential device failures	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC3P2R27	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The participants must be able to control the IoT devices/sensors through the XR platform e.g. with their gestures.	To support actuations	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC3P2R28	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The participants must be able to attend the remote business meeting using one or more devices among a variety of VR/AR or legacy devices supported by the system e.g. desktop, cellphone, VR glasses.	To support seamless integration between legacy and XR platforms	01-Mandatory	ICOM
UC3P2R29	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a participant, I want to share documents to other participants		01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P2R30	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a virtual assistant, I want to be able to access the documents shared in the meeting	This will allow the virtual assistant to summarize the documents	01-Mandatory	CEA

UC3P2R31	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a virtual assistant, I want to be able to provide summaries of the documents shared in the meeting		01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P2R32	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a virtual assistant, I want to receive streams of text in real time from each participant		01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P2R33	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a virtual assistant, I want to be able to speak up to provide assistance when needed		01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P2R34	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The system must make explicit the fact that a given participant is a virtual assistant		01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P2R35	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The system must send voice streams of each participant to the speech to text system	To be able to implement all speech related features	01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P2R36	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The system must transfer transcribed speech streams of each participant to the participants that need them	To be able to implement the virtual assistant	01-Mandatory	CEA
UC3P1R01	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow users (meeting organizer) to log into their account by entering their email and password.	Only by registred users can use Cortex2 application	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA
UC3P1R03	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow the user (organizer of the meeting) to create a XR business meeting room.	in order to set up the XR environment and choose the features to be used for this meeting (especially to preserve bandwidth)	01-Mandatory	LINAGORA

UC3P1R02	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow users (meeting organizer) to log in with OpenID accounts.	To facilitate resgitation and login	02-Optional	LINAGORA
UC3P1R02	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow users (meeting organizer) to log in with OpenID accounts.	To facilitate resgitation and login	02-Optional	LINAGORA
UC3P1R05	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow the user (organizer) to invite participants to an existing XR business meeting room	To increase usability	03-Desirable	LINAGORA
UC3P1R09	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Meeting orgnaisze must be able to define what participants are allowed to do in business meeting environment	to avoid conflicting collaborative usage	03-Desirable	LINAGORA
UC3P2R22	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The participants should be able to switch between first person view and global view		03-Desirable	DFKI
UC3P2R01	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Cortex2 should allow users (meeting participants) to log in to a business meeting room with meeting link	To be able participating to a meeting	03-Desirable	LINAGORA
UC3P2R10	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting participant should be able to send private message to another participant	To be able having private discussion	03-Desirable	LINAGORA
UC3P2R14	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	Business meeting participant should be able to join the business meeting using cellphone	To be using only phone call	03-Desirable	LINAGORA

UC3P2R18	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The participant which uses cellphone could be able to rise hand using voice command	To provide such feature for users with no interface	03-Desirable	LINAGORA
UC3P2R19	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The participants could be able to work around a white board	To enhance collaboration	03-Desirable	LINAGORA
UC3P2R20	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The XR business room should be customizable (look and feel, objects, furniture, accessories)	To create personalized rooms	03-Desirable	DFKI
UC3P2R23	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The participants joining with a video stream can choose their appearance (standard, other person, anonymity preserving participation, representation by a video avatar)		03-Desirable	DFKI
UC3P2R33	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a virtual assistant, I want to be able to post written messages to provide assistance when needed		03-Desirable	CEA
UC3P2R34	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As a virtual assistant, I want to be able to access the intranet/internet to search for information useful for the other participants		03-Desirable	CEA
UC3P2R35	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	As an organizer, I want to be able to (temporarily) disable the virtual assistant participant	Some participants can refuse the interaction with such an agent or some data can be considered as too sensitive to send them to a virtual agent	03-Desirable	CEA

UC3P2R39	P3: Business Meeting Pilot	The system must transfer the result of gestures analysis to the participants that need them	To enrich the virtual assistant	03-Desirable	CEA
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10. Annex B: Table of Non-Functional Requirements

The following table lists the identified non-functional requirements.

Table 10: Non-functional requirements

ID	Description	Rationale	Priority	Elicited By
<i>Unique identifier</i>	<i>High level process, function or capability that the requirement addresses.</i>	<i>Why is this requirement needed?</i>	<i>Priority of this requirement: Mandatory Desirable Optional</i>	<i>Who captured the requirement?</i>
NFUC1V1R01	The on-field technician can use a VR headset with see-through capability or a smartphone/tablet	multi-platform, Head Mounted display (HMD)	Mandatory	ALCATEL
NFUC1V1R02	The system shall manage the reference view and where to set the AR items	unity 3D , scene synchro	Mandatory	ALCATEL
NFUC1V1R03	Cortex platform shall provide DSL scripting for XR modules interaction		Mandatory	ALCATEL
NFUC1V1R04	Cortex platform shall provide a storing / Database where to store the 3D models + possible avatars		Mandatory	ALCATEL
NFUC1V1R05	Cortex platform shall provide low latency in media treatment		Mandatory	ALCATEL
NFUC1V1R06	Scene context persistence	for "history" context for newly connected users	Mandatory	ALCATEL

NFUC2S1R01	VR controller support for VR trainee application	to facilitate interaction for the trainee	Mandatory	ACTIMAGE
NFUC2S1R02	Low latency in video, audio, 3D object and screen cast transfer	to allow real-time conversations	Mandatory	ACTIMAGE
NFUC2S1R03	Easy-to use application interface and interconnectability	to make using the platform easy	Desirable	ACTIMAGE
NFUC3P1R02	A participant must be able to attend a business meeting using one or more device among a variety of VR/AR or legacy devices supported by the system e.g. desktop, laptop, cellphone, VR glasses, hand sensor.		Mandatory	ICOM
NFUC3P1R01	XR business meeting room shall follow the Cortex application model and objects	Business meeting is Cortex application	Mandatory	LINAGORA
NFUC3P2R01	When an avatar rise a hand, the rise status button in the interface should be also updated	To synchronize with people using legacy devices	Mandatory	LINAGORA
NFUC3P2R02	If a voice command is detected the status of the user should be updated accordingly	To synchronize with people using legacy devices	Mandatory	LINAGORA
NFUC1UC2UC3	IoT Devices/sensors of heterogeneous IoT protocols (e.g. WiFi) must be supported by the system.		Mandatory	ICOM

11. Annex C: Social, ethical and legal requirements

The following table lists the social requirements

Table 11: Social requirements

ID	Description	Rationale	Priority	Elicited By
<i>Unique identifier</i>	<i>High level process, function or capability that the requirement addresses.</i>	<i>Why is this requirement needed?</i>	<i>Priority of this requirement: Mandatory Desirable Optional</i>	<i>Who captured the requirement?</i>
SFUJIR01	To achieve a high user presence (avatars in a scene with interactable objects) without increasing the variables that cause fatigue. To avoid or reduce: --The delay between the user's actions and the avatar's actions. --La vergence-accommodation conflict (VAC). --Avoid unnecessary movements in the scenes so as not to produce dizziness.	To reduce fatigue caused by virtual reality and augmented reality technology.	Mandatory	UJI
SFUJIR02	Include maximum usage time reminders when using VR.	To reduce the fatigue caused by the time of use of this technology.	Desirable	UJI
SFUJIR03	Pay special attention to the quality of the training prior to the use of technology. That is, include an appropriate tutorial that includes the benefits they will get by using the technology. In addition, include	To reduce the technostress	Mandatory	UJI

	access to help during its use of easy access.			
SFUJIR04	Evaluate the use of hyper-realistic or realistic avatars, taking into account that the difference does not have great weight in the user presence and taking into account that an extreme realism of your own body can generate technostress.	To reduce the technostress	Desirable	UJI
SFUJIR05	Provide a privacy option and not save the objects uploaded by users in the database and/or that they are deleted at the end of the session (for example for when a user wants to enter an object for a meeting, but it is "secret").	To reduce technostress, specifically the fear of theft of ideas.	Optional	UJI
SFUJIR06	We have to be careful when creating the assistant so that it generates the desired trust in users: --The assistant needs a natural human body and behavior. --The use of a human voice is preferable to a mechanized voice. --Use a calm and reliable tone. --The user should not perceive that the assistant intends to deceive him.	To improve the learning of technology and thus, reduce the technostress.	Desirable	UJI

The following table lists the ethical and legal requirements

Table 12: Ethical and legal requirements

ID	Description	Rationale	Priority	Elicited By
<i>Unique identifier</i>	<i>High level process, function or capability that the requirement addresses.</i>	<i>Why is this requirement needed?</i>	<i>Priority of this requirement: Mandatory Desirable Optional</i>	<i>Who captured the requirement?</i>
NFEKUL01	Inclusiveness and accessibility requirements: include features like text to speech ,and other feature that ensure that the framework accommodates users with a range of disabilities including auditory, cognitive, physical, neurological , visual and speech disabilities	to ensure that the CORTEX framework does not replicate the social biases, inequalities and skewed power relations that exist in the physical world	desirable	KUL
NFEKUL02	User safety: a feature to moderate and reasonably customise user interactions to ensure that safety concerns that are typical in online space such as harassment , obscenities and derogatory comments about an individual's race, religion, gender, sexual identity, nationality or disability.	To ensure a safe immersive environment for using by providing a means to address and minimise antisocial behaviour.	mandatory	KUL
NFLKUL01	Security featurers to prevent impersonation and identity theft and a way to authenticate users	cases of identity theft and impersonation can lead to economic loss or loss of life. such as the impersonation of a trainer.	mandatory	KUL

NFLKUL02	Include the possibility of customising the avatars and accomodate cases where the uses mayneed to obfuscate their appearance	In instance of facial reconstruction users may have legitimate reasons like medical conditions , in exercise of their right to not reavel sensitive informaion like race or gender., it should be possible to modify the hyper-realistic avaters.	Mandatory	KUL
NFLKUL03	Data minimisation principle enshrined in the GDPR: in the course of the processing activities envisaged in CORTEX2, only data that is necessary to intended aim of the processing activities	compliance with the GDPR	Mandatory	KUL

12. Annex D: Feature and components tables

The following table lists the features derived from the requirements

Table 13: List of features

Unique identifier	Feature	Related requirements
F01	User registration and authentication using email and password or voice including avatar setup,	UC3P1R01, UC3P2R04, UC3P2R22, UC1V1R16

F02	XR environment setup and configuration by admin user or cortex session initiator	UC3P1R03, UC3P1R04, UC3P1R06, UC3P1R07, UC3P1R08, UC3P1R08
F03	Cortex clients synchronization (signaling, presence, avatar, rendering, annotations, etc.) across the network	UC3P2R02, UC3P2R03, UC3P2R05, UC3P2R16, UC1V1R44
F04	Audio collaborative conversation	UC3P2R06, UC2S1R12, UC2S1R13
F05	Screen sharing including gestures (expert hand for example)	UC3P2R07, UC1V1R21, UC1V1R47, UC1V2R01, UC1V2R04, UC1V2R03, UC1V2R04
F06	Video sharing	UC3P2R08, UC1V1R11, UC2S1R12, UC2S1R13
F07	Textual sharing (chat / white board / annotation etc.) including response, deleting, etc.	UC3P2R09, UC1V1R45
F08	Meeting summarization	UC3P2R11, UC1V1R12
F09	User IoT device interaction (door ringing, lamp, smart-phone, etc.) tracking/action from Cortex application (VR/AR/Legacy)	UC3P2R12, UC3P2R13, UC1V1R15, UC1V1R20, UC1V1R22
F10	Avatar gestures (rising hand)	UC3P2R17
F11	Voice user interface	UC1V2R01
F12	Interaction with Virtual objects including annotation with arrows, etc.	UC1V1R15, UC1V2R02, UC1V2R03
F13	Audio /video recording	UC1V1R17
F14	Drawing or messaging	UC1V1R18
F15	Local files access (open, select, share)	UC1V1R18
F16	Possibility to take and annotate of snapshots	UC1V1R19

F17	Augmented information assist	UC1V1R29
F18	XR Object scanning, matching with existing objects and annotation (On, Off)	UC1V1R42, UC1V1R43, UC1V1R44, UC1V1R45
F19	Real environment sensing mainly for AR , an action in real world might produce an effect in virtual world	UC1V1R46
F20	Real world reconstruction	UC1V2R02, UC2S1R21
F21	screen (image, ++) compression to save band width	UC1V3R01
F22	Distant control (send commands from one device to another in remote mode)	UC2S1R14
F23	Scene models loading (for training example)	UC2S1R21
F24	IoT objects discovery and control	UC3P2R24, UC3P2R27
F25	Rendering IoT information	UC3P2R25
F26	Personal conversational assistant	UC3P2R29-36

The following table lists the components and modules of the architecture associated to features

Table 14: List of components and modules of the architecture

Component ID	Component name	Layer	Module ID	Module name	Related Features	Related components
C01	Cortex authentication	Client	C01M01	User Registration Client-side	F01	
C02	User Management	Server	C02M01	User Registration Server-side	F01	CORTEX2-DB
C01	Cortex authentication	Client	C01M02	User Authentication Client-side	F01	
C02	User Management	Server	C02M02	User Authentication Server-side	F01	CORTEX2-DB
C01	Cortex authentication	Client	C01M03	User Role assignment Client-side	F01	
C02	User Management	Server	C02M03	User Role assignment Server-side	F01	CORTEX2-DB
C01	Cortex authentication	Client	C01M04	User appearance selection Client-side	F01	
C02	User Management	Server	C02M04	User appearance selection Server-side	F01	CORTEX2-DB
C01	Cortex authentication	Client	C01M05	Avatar construction from webcam and saving to store	F01	CORTEX2-DB
C03	Video compression	Client	C03M01	Video compression and alternative appearance (VCAA) Client	F21	
C03	Video compression	Server	C03M02	Video compression and alternative appearance (VCAA) - XR Service	F21	
C04	Cortex Speech	Client	C04M01	Cortex Speech Prefabs	F11	

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C04	Cortex Speech	Server	C04M02	Cortex Speech Technologies Services	F11	
C05	Cortex Virtual Assets	Client	C05M01	Application 3D/2D scene assets	F02	
C05	Cortex Virtual Assets	Server	C05M02	Data management		CORTEX2-DB
C06	Cortex 3D reconstruction	Client	C06M01	Cortex Scene - Client side	F23	
C06	Cortex 3D reconstruction	Server	C06M02	Reconstruction XR service		
C06	Cortex 3D reconstruction	Server	C06M03	Data Management for storage		CORTEX2-DB
C07	SceneManagment	Server	C07M01	Scene synchronization	F03	MediaAndModalityManagment, DeviceSceneManagment
C07	SceneManagment	Client	C07M02	Scene changes tracking and update	F03, F12, F14	MediaAndModalityManagment, DeviceSceneManagment
C08	MediaAndModalityTunneling	Client	C08M01	Cortex Rainbow SDK Media and data transport	F04, F06,F07	
C08	MediaAndModalityTunneling	Server	C08M02	Rainbow SDK / Rainbow core	F04, F06,F07	

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C09	AR tracking and synchronization	Client	C09M01	AR Pose Tracking	F05, F10, F18, F19, F20	
C09	AR tracking and synchronization	Server	C09M02	Scene Synchronization (Server)	F05, F10, F18, F19, F20	
C10	Meeting summarization	Server	C10M01	Meeting summarization service	F08	
C11	IoTManagment	Client	C11M01	Cortex IoT SDK (Client)	F09, F24, F25	Cortex Speech, Virtual assistant
C11	IoTManagment	Server	C11M02	IoT Device Management		
C11	IoTManagment	Server	C11M03	Cortex IoT Server service	F09	IoT Server
C12	SessionRecording	Client	C12M01	Cortex Rainbow SDK Media and data transport	F13	CORTEX-DB
C12	SessionRecording	Server	C12M02	Rainbow SDK / Rainbow core	F13	CORTEX-DB
C13	SceneManagment	Client	C13M01	File access	F15	CORTEX-DB, Cortex Speech
C13	SceneManagment	Server	C13M01	DB access control	F15	CORTEX-DB
C13	SceneManagment	Client	C13M02	Augmented information assistance	F17	CORTEX-DB, Cortex Speech
C13	SceneManagment	Server	C13M02	DB access control	F17	CORTEX-DB

C14	Virtual assistant	Client	C13M03	Conversational assistance	F26	CORTEX-DB, Cortex Speech, 3rd party services (agenda, etc.)
C14	Document summarization	Server	C13M04	Document summarization service	F26	